

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

Document D6.4 Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighboring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The objective of deliverable D6.4 is to report on the updates of the NEANIAS architecture, specifications and software development plan of the Core Services developed in WP6. This document reports on the updated general design principles, the overall system architecture and fundamental resources with respect to D6.1. Then it presents the current status of the released core services related to manage Open Science lifecycle (C1), EOSC integration (C2), Artificial Intelligence processing (C3) and, finally, Visualization (C4).

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The NEANIAS WP6 “Core Services Foundation and Implementation” establishes generic, cross-community services that amplify the potential of thematic services delivered by WP2-4 and business services delivered in WP5, enabling Open Science, and facilitating the migration to the EOSC concepts, by streamlining access to cloud resources.

In particular Task 6.1 “Service gap analysis and specifications” builds on the requirements delivered by the community sector WPs (WP2, WP3 and WP4) and those delivered by innovation cases in WP5. It also utilizes the information gathered by WP8 on EOSC hub landscape and trends and consortium knowledge and acquaintance with Research Infrastructures (RIs). It locates and highlight the gap from Open Science principles as augmented by the vision of NEANIAS, and deliver specifications that bridge the gap. The task is also responsible for drafting an implementation roadmap with consolidated contribution from all other tasks of the WP, aligned to the milestones and to the research sector development plans, able to achieve delivery of software artefacts in due time for service delivery by WP7.

Task 6.2 “Architecture and interoperability approach design and validation” builds on outcomes of T6.1 and input coming from other work packages and yields the architecture of NEANIAS framework and the set of its service set, covering both, core and thematic ones, towards a holistic architectural alignment of its services. It sets the principles for interoperability of services, both internally as well as externally. With a strong preference in well-established standards, it presents options that services shall adopt for maximising their interoperability and reuse opportunities. Core service implementation tasks T6.3-6 build on top of the outputs from T6.1 and T6.2, aligning core services to the NEANIAS framework.

Two core services (C1 and C2) are dictated by the needs and opportunities raised in EOSC. C1, provided by Task 6.3, includes research lifecycle empowering services, providing essential tools for registering, locating, inspecting, sharing data and services. C2, provided by Task 6.4, allows for EOSC/RIs Integration services for the exploitation of EOSC and RIs offerings in a unified manner for NEANIAS services, including access to storage and computation and mechanisms for authentication and authorization. Abstracting on thematic service concepts and analyzing the opportunities of innovation on EOSC, the other two services (C3 and C4) are the arrowhead of NEANIAS generic service offerings. C3 includes AI services provided by Task T6.5 that enclose also capacities for Machine Learning and C4 offers Visualisation services provided by Task 6.6 that deliver state-of-the-art visualization as a service.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

This deliverable D6.4 reports the updates with respect to the ones reported in deliverable D6.1 [1] i.e. the core services design principles and system architecture, and specifications led by Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 including a detailed description and updated implementation plan for C1/C2/C3/C4 core services developed in Tasks 6.3, 6.4, 6.5 and 6.6.

1.3. Structure of the document

In Section 2 the updates since deliverable D6.1 are summarized. In Section 3 updates on service design principles are reported, including the Service Oriented Architecture paradigm guidelines, REST paradigm, Standards and Interoperability guidelines. Section 4 describes the overall current status of the NEANIAS System Architecture including the logical architecture, a generic service processing lifecycle and the physical deployment. Section 5 focuses on the NEANIAS fundamental resources abstractions, namely storage and computation. Chapters 6, 7, 8, 9 presents the Core Services C1, C2, C3 and C4 respectively, detailing, in tabular format, all the main information regarding e.g. technologies adopted, dependencies with other core services, licensing etc. A work plan of the delivered services together with the proposed timeline is presented in Section 10. Finally, Section 11 provides conclusions and plans for the future activities.

2. Updates since D6.1

2.1. Design Principles

The Design Principles as reported in D6.1 drive the non-functional aspects of the NEANIAS software development lifecycle and have been (or being) adopted in the development of the services. This section has not been modified since Deliverable 6.1 and, for clarity reason and to keep this document self-consistent, it is included in the current deliverable as well.

2.2. Fundamental Resources Abstractions

The resource abstractions reported in D6.1 have been made more general and infrastructure independent, leaving out platform specific details, which can be found in D7.4 [2]. Moreover, the section which reports on resource abstractions has been completed with diagrams, to enhance clarity.

2.3. System Architecture

NEANIAS logical architecture has evolved since its first definition, to accommodate the evolution of services and interconnections performed to address challenges or adapt to the evolving environment the project operates in. Several services have been regrouped either under an originating technology (services offered by Zenodo and respective integration layers) or under a concept (L3 infrastructure services). The computation abstraction layer has evolved to embrace the containerization and deployment approaches adopted, as the needs of services for access to resources and the delivery policies of the project have been finalized. New services have been positioned on the logical structure of the project, while others were removed, representing the changes in NEANIAS services' set.

The presentation of the logical architecture has been reshaped for better readability and representation of the aforementioned changes.

2.4. C1 Open-Science lifecycle support services updates

C1 Open-Science lifecycle support service have been further developed in the first period of the project. The NEANIAS service catalogue portal and APIs underlying models and functionality have been extended and customized in order to comply to the EOSC Profiles 3.0 specifications (<https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation>) and to support the classification of NEANIAS services into the three main thematic areas of NEANIAS project (Space, Underwater, Atmospheric). Zenodo repository service has been employed for the NEANIAS data catalogue and PID service. As part of C1 services, a palette of common and reusable UI\UX elements have been prepared, which are already employed by thematic service providers for the presentation of their services and the development of uniform user journeys. The Argos service provided by OpenAIRE is already operating and offers NEANIAS service owners the ability to create and maintain actionable Data Management Plans. A new plan is settled for MS6 and MS7, as development has already covered its initial targets and new requests are gathered. Finally, the data validation service as a core service for data producers of thematic services to validate their data against metadata schemes has not been highlighted as a priority by users of the thematic services. The scope, functionality, and further

development of this service will be reassessed based on the requirements and the ongoing development of the thematic services.

2.5. C2 EOSC hub, RIs and cloud integration enabling services updates

Evolution in C2 services has been significant in the first period of the project.

AAI service has evolved to match best practices (e.g. dropping support for API Keys in favor of Client Credential Grants, which is conformant with the OpenID Connect protocol) while it has employed new strategies and features to facilitate accounting and user information handling on behalf of services. On the other hand, for selected low-level services, support for AAI was dropped, in favor of other technologies, in order to avoid loops of dependencies. Log aggregation service underwent minor changes in favor of performance (e.g. dropping http API) and offers new unplanned services, such as the ability to limit access to its gathered logs for users, which is an innovation of the service. Accounting service, was realigned to service implementer's needs, taking a form that does not interfere with their implementation plan and does not create strong dependencies. This has been achieved by collecting data indirectly from each service. Furthermore, it adds a whole suit of new tools for exploring and using the accounting data by its clients.

At lower level, the GARR Container Platform service has been extended with 2 new virtual Kubernetes clusters dedicated to the NEANIAS staging and production environments covering the increasing project's service's needs.

Two services have been removed, namely the Data Avenue and the MiCADO services. According to the original plan Data Avenue service provides high-level data transfer service for users, however the development directions showed that the most user-friendly way to access data on storages is to use mounting mechanism. As a result, the Data Transfer service is not needed anymore. MiCADO is able to provide dynamically scaling kubernetes cluster on various cloud resources, however the GARR services proved to be a stable and well useable alternative to MiCADO, therefore the focus turned to the GARR provided kubernetes platform. On the other hand, an additional service has been added for allowing other services to send out e-mail messages on behalf of the NEANIAS domain.

Last but not least, few additional subsystems are under consideration:

- A subsystem for delegating AAI management, that may be offered to service providers controlling of user attributes without administrative access.
- A user profile management subsystem that will centrally allow services to deposit user preferences.
- A subsystem that allows data publishing and metadata validation in one step, to simplify thematic services' interaction with data publishing service.

Implementation will be launched after prioritization and upon resources availability.

2.6. C3 Artificial Intelligence services updates

C3 services have been developed towards improving the integration with the computational and storage resources. The services are better utilising GARR resources such as bare metal Kubernetes, OpenStack Kubernetes and cloud resources. The four services have been

improved in different fields like utilization of docker registry, https support, remote storage mounting support, added demo applications and improving their specific features. All the four services have been significantly updated; details can be found in Section 8.

2.7. C4 Visualisation services updates

C4 Visualisation services have been mainly updated toward addressing i) the integration with the NEANIAS overall delivery and operational infrastructure and ii) user requirements coming from the thematic services. The C4.1 Visual Discovery Framework has been further developed toward addressing the visualization needs of the Space (VD-VisIVO and VD-Splotch) and Underwater (VD-MAPS) community by providing a user-friendly User Interface and demo data for service showcasing and by integrating with the other core services mainly for providing federated access, data sharing, logging and accounting. The C4.2 Visualization Gateway has been extended for supporting the access to the Visual Discovery Framework customizing the JupyterHub platform on the NEANIAS Kubernetes cluster integrating the NEANIAS AAI and the Data Sharing service. In C4.3 both the planned modules, the Position Manager Service (PMS) and the Data Connector Service (DCS), have been deployed on staging environment. both modules have been integrated with AAI core services, logging and accounting.

3. Design Principles

This section reports the design principles of the Core Services and overall NEANIAS architecture based on Service Oriented Architecture (including the list of minimum services required), REST (REpresentational State Transfer) paradigm, FAIR principles (to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and User Interface guidelines. This section also details on main aspects regarding pluggability, extensibility, interoperability, portability, security, operation and technology.

3.1. Service Oriented Architecture

Service Oriented Architectures (SOA) are driven by several principles that although varying in number have a core notion of service reuse, separation, discoverability, interoperability etc.

NEANIAS adopts the Service Oriented Architecture paradigm guidelines, with varying degree of enforcement and the addition of microservices. Furthermore, it adds its own principles for services matured and delivered in the context of NEANIAS.

Essential motivations behind the adopted approach are the following:

- NEANIAS builds on existing services of substantial maturity that act in coordination with other systems, implying a completely different paradigm of software architecture.
- Services in the context of NEANIAS and EOSC do not adhere to the notion of services as expressed in the SOA paradigm. As such their granularity, model of operation and interaction is quite different than in common SOA services.
- A subset of NEANIAS infrastructure requires a level of integration among specific services which in cases may compromise the loosely coupling and isolation principles.
- NEANIAS policy with respect to service dependencies promote standards vs custom service contracts and attempts to isolate services sustainability risks with a number of techniques that drive the technological choices behind specific lower-level infrastructure services.

In the following we briefly present the SOA principles adopted in NEANIAS:

- **Contracts:** Services will present clear definitions of their interfaces and their expected interaction patterns that they will respect. In NEANIAS the following policies shall be respected:
 - o The primary candidate interface form for services shall be compliant with REST, although reasonable exceptions may apply.
 - o Services shall respect their interface contracts and apply to the best of abilities backwards compatibility among their versions. Compatibility shall be clearly declared in their contract.
 - o Where well-known or de-facto standards apply for interfaces of specific services, those will be adopted.
- **Discoverability:** NEANIAS services shall be registered in central repository so that they can be found and invoked by other services. The principle is enforced for top level services or services that are enabling the infrastructure; however, it is not imposed for microservices that might be supporting a service. Furthermore, static and dynamic registration are both valid approaches due to the assumptions of specific services. All

services will start from 0-point assumptions declared in their base configuration. In NEANIAS there will be the following classes of services with respect to discoverability:

- **Fixed EndPoint Services:** Services that respond to a predefined endpoint. Registration may be performed statically and is optional.
- **Dynamic EndPoint Services:** Services that register themselves into the infrastructure service instance catalogue upon instantiation and need to be discovered to be exploited.
- **Loose Coupling:** Services shall not be making any further assumption on their dependencies other than the ones declared in their interaction contract, so that the services may be substituted by other services. The principle is suggested yet not enforced in NEANIAS as there are several services that make deep assumptions on microservices they utilize, which themselves may be independent services. Loose coupling is a strong asset for service sustainability as it helps reduce risks. However, in NEANIAS it is also assumed that most services will conform to a few internal behavioral contracts. Those relate to security, accounting, logging, etc.
- **Encapsulation:** Services should not be exposing to their consumers details on how they perform their tasks. However, this is not a strongly imposed principle as services may be assuming specific features of services they depend on. It is suggested that services expose their internal features that clients may wish to depend on, in the registration service, so that they can be explored by clients.
- **Reusability:** Services in NEANIAS are suggested to be defined in a manner that maximizes reusability. This is essential for all major identified services of the ecosystem; however, it is not enforced for microservices underlying those which may be tailored to specific tasks.
- **Statelessness:** Services, to the best of their efforts shall assume no state maintenance among their invocations. However, this may not be semantically feasible as services may be depending on data that grow via subsequent invocations and although stateless in their interface, they are not stateless internally. Supporting services will also need to handle state in more than few examples. Thus, although a good practice statelessness is not enforced. In technical terms NEANIAS promotes the REST paradigm for service interactions which further supports this directive.
- **Autonomy:** Services have control on the logic they encapsulate and define their terms of operation. The principle is not generally adopted by NEANIAS but may be followed by specific services for their specific mission critical and, in exceptional occasions, sustainability reasons.
- **Composability:** Services should be allowing callers to compose them into larger logic workflows to carry out composite tasks. The principle is not only strongly suggested in NEANIAS, but it is also supported by several architecture design choices that allow services to be composed building on assumptions on fundamental concepts, such as security.

3.2. Minimum service requirements

All NEANIAS services **must conform** with the following requirements:

- Present their users with a clear and definite **Terms of Use** text that defines intended use and clarifies how the service may be used, presents its Service Level Agreement (SLA) and the data protection rules applied, and if applicable exemplifies and discourages potential malicious use.
- Adopt the **Authentication Authorization Infrastructure** (AAI) policies and protocols established in NEANIAS core AAI and conform to one of the AuthN/AuthZ models introduced in this report and follow its evolution in the course of project's agile design and development activities.
- Generate all **accounting** information required for the infrastructure, among others, to evaluate the use of resources, calculate KPIs and potentially, in the future, apply quotas to resource usage.
- Take all **security** measures to:
 - Comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the policies settled by the project.
 - Respect and enforce data protection assumptions made and declared to end users.
 - Prevent infrastructure from malicious use, especially from its own internal logic and to its best effort by its users.
 - Utilize resources placed at their disposal in compliance with resource provider's policies.
- Respond to handling any major direct or indirect (i.e. dependencies) security defects identified by other partners and 3rd parties.

Furthermore, NEANIAS services are **encouraged** to:

- Provide standard **logging** information that ships to central log analysis facility for consolidated log analysis and troubleshooting.
- Adopt cloudification strategies that allow them to scale up and down with needs.
- Seek and adopt official or de fact standards for
 - data they generate and/or consume.
 - any interaction with other services, unless such specifications are outdated and do not comply with modern technologies and service needs.
- Adopt Open Science policies, such as publishing their output data in catalogues:
 - Register metadata in catalogues, presenting enough evidence for discovery but also identification the origin and process of the data they refer to.
 - Register data in long term data repositories suggested by the project.
- Adopt the most portable supported model suitable for their operation and needs.

3.3. REST paradigm

NEANIAS services as well as the existing EOSC services are employing well-established web technologies, i.e. HTTP REST for the implementation of their API methods. An API (Application Programming Interface) is a protocol intended to be used as an interface by software components to communicate with each other. **RE**presentational **S**tate **T**ransfer (**REST**) is an architectural style, or design pattern, for APIs. REST specifies a few architectural constraints

that must be satisfied for an API to be referred to as RESTful. These constraints, such as client-server stateless interactions, cacheable resources, layered system and uniform interface, when applied to a web service induce desirable properties, such as performance, scalability, and modifiability, that enable services to work best on the Web.

In the REST architectural style, data and functionality are considered resources and are accessed using Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs), typically links on the Web. When a RESTful API is called, the server will transfer to the client a representation of the state of the requested resource. The resources are acted upon by using a set of simple, well-defined operations. In the REST architecture style, clients and servers exchange representations of resources by using a standardized interface and protocol. The REST architectural style is designed to use a stateless communication protocol, typically HTTP. HTTP defines a set of request methods to indicate the desired action to be performed for a given service resource. Each of these methods (referred to as HTTP verbs) implements a different action. The primary or most-commonly-used HTTP verbs are POST, GET, PUT, PATCH and DELETE. These correspond to create, read, update, and delete (or CRUD) operations.

Some common design best practices used when designing REST APIs are:

- Use of the JSON standard for transferring data. There are other ways to transfer data as for example XML, however they are not as widely supported by frameworks.
- Use of nouns instead of verbs for defining resources that make sense from the perspective of the API consumer. This is preferred because HTTP request methods already include verbs. For example, a resource could be called “users” and the action GET /users could retrieve a list of all users.
- Use of standard HTTP error codes as response codes when an error occurs.
- Use of SSL/TLS for security for the REST APIs to communicate over secure channels and protect information exchanged.
- Use of API versioning for API updates in order to make the transition to new versions smoothly and prevent invalid requests to updated endpoints.
- Use of data caching to improve performance.
- Use of data filtering, sorting and pagination to improve performance especially when there is too much data to be returned all at once.

3.4. Pluggability & Extensibility

Pluggability and extensibility are key design principles for building EOSC services for NEANIAS. For the long-term development strategy of a service, the capability for functional updates and extensions must be provided in order to implement the newly arising users' demands in a seamless way.

While extensibility enables developers to expand or add capabilities of a service without modifying the original source code, pluggability is one of the possible approaches to support

it via a pluggable framework and plugins. The two together are the capability to add new modules to a service without recompiling or even restarting a running service.

Modularity is an important aspect of the service architecture in order to serve pluggability and extensibility with low development effort. In order to provide this, the application of microservices architecture design is highly recommended. In microservice architecture, multiple loosely coupled services work together. Each service focuses on a single purpose and has a high cohesion of related behaviors and data.

The main motivations for microservices architecture to support pluggability and extensibility are as follows:

- **Modularity:** Each microservice represents a logically cohesive, lightweight and independent business functionality with well-defined boundaries. By design, microservices are highly granular, and independently built and deployed.
- **Loose coupling:** Microservices are designed to be loosely coupled with minimal dependency on other services and libraries.
- **Extensibility:** Microservices can be leveraged to create an extensible solution by quickly onboarding newer ones.
- **Communication:** Microservices can be effectively built by using communication standards such as REST.

Communication between microservices and with client applications has to happen fast with low overhead (e.g. no server-side session management and lean message structure) and network latency, REST APIs are a good fit. Beyond performance, applying RESTful API is also a key factor to support the aforementioned key features. For details on REST API, please see Section 2.3.

3.5. Interoperability

Interoperability is usually considered as the ability to interconnect data, services and e-infrastructures. The key to exchange data among components in an e-infrastructure is the utilization of standards in communication and data format.

Interoperability is one of the most important aspects in EOSC, where the aim is to build a huge European-wide e-infrastructure for scientists to exchange data, services and resources. In order to realize this goal, the EOSC Pilot¹ project investigated the most typical reasons for non-interoperability happening in e-infrastructures (see link below). The reasons are identified and named by 6 different gaps along with 6 risks behind the gaps. To lower the risks preventing infrastructures' interoperability, the EOSC pilot project defined 14 recommendations to ensure infrastructure's interoperability. Finally, 6 recommendations were stated to adapt FAIR data principles for the EOSC.

¹ <https://eosc-pilot.eu/>

The FAIR Data Principles are guidelines to make data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. However, concerning EOSC, it is important to complement the FAIR principles with further recommendations that improve the availability of research data to users and services through an open cloud infrastructure. These recommendations can be found at <https://eoscpilot.eu/eoscpilot%E2%80%99s-contributions-eosc-interoperability>. Section 3.7 will detail how these principles are being implemented in the core services.

3.6. Standards

All core services are delivered according to standards, on the direction to support the targeted research sectors (WP2, WP3, WP4) and communities as well as the targeted additional business cases (WP5).

NEANIAS vision on EOSC is the full compliance with capable and prominent standards and widely adopted specifications, as the only road towards wide and undoubtable interoperability means. Thus, it plans to not only adopt but also, where needed, to propose augmentation of models and specifications, promote the use by engaged stakeholders and where ground is found to propose new approaches capable of being standardized in the future. The establishment of strategic synergies with relevant national, European and international initiatives, is essential element to achieve this impact; those synergies target both the reuse of tools and services from EOSC, Research Infrastructures and other domains, based on commonly agreed protocols, and the establishment/expansion of working groups in areas of interest. Research Data Alliance (RDA) participation in areas such as Array Database Assessment, Data Management Plan (DMP) Common Standards, as well as groups dealing with data identification, description, provenance and quality are being actively followed.

As already mentioned in Deliverable D9.1 [4], NEANIAS partners are significantly linked to several standardization consortium and organizations toward sustainability and interoperability, such as the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), the Open Navigation Surface (ONS), the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA), the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) and the OpenID Foundation (OIDF).

Some of the standards that are adopted in NEANIAS services are as listed below, but the list is not meant to be exhaustive and is expected to be extended during the development:

- IETF OAuth2: An open standard for authentication / authorization.
- OpenID: An open standard for authentication.
- OGC WMS: An open standard for rendering of digital maps composed of raster and vector data.
- OGC WFS: A standard interface allowing requests for geographical features across the web using platform-independent calls.
- OGC WCS: An Interface Standard that defines Web-based retrieval of digital geospatial information representing space/time-varying phenomena.
- OGC WPS: An Interface Standard that provides rules for standardizing inputs and outputs, and relative requests and responses, for geospatial processing services.

- OGC WMTS: A standard protocol for serving pre-rendered or run-time computed georeferenced map tiles.
- OGC GeoTIFF: An open standard managing the Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) for the exchange of georeferenced or geocoded imagery.
- OGC GeoPackage: An open, non-proprietary, platform-independent and standards-based data format for geographic information system implemented as SQLite database container.
- OGC 3D Tiles: A standard for streaming and rendering massive 3D geospatial data using tiled hierarchical data structures.
- IVOA SAMP: An open standard messaging protocol that enables astronomy software tools to interoperate and communicate.
- IVOA TAP: An open standard interface providing a general access mechanism for tabular data, including but not limited to astronomical catalogs.
- IVOA VOTable: An XML based standard for the interchange of data represented as a set of tables, with particular emphasis on astronomical tables.
- FITS: An open standard format and transport system used in astronomy data.
- OSGeo TMS: A specification for tiled web maps.
- ONS BAG: A file format designed to store and exchange bathymetric data.
- Unidata NetCDF: A community standard for sharing array-oriented scientific data.
- OAI-PMH: A protocol for harvesting metadata descriptions of records in an archive so that services can be built using metadata from many archives.
- EOSC-EDMI²: a minimum information metadata guideline defined by EOSCpilot to help users and services to find and access datasets reusing existing data models and interfaces.

And many other standards related to the W3C recommendations and protocols such as HTML5/JavaScript/CSS3, JSON, XML, HTTP(S) and FTP.

3.7. F.A.I.R. principles

This section describes how the principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) are supported by each of the NEANIAS core services belonging to C1, C2, C3, and C4. Those details complement information included in D1.5 presenting the overall NEANIAS Data Management Plan.

3.7.1. C1 core services

FAIR data principles are followed by all C1 core services.

Findable. Access to the service catalogue and service metadata is provided through the NEANIAS service catalogue portal. The NEANIAS portal offers browsing and keyword search functionality to enable users to discover and find services in an intuitive manner. The service catalogue adopts the guidelines posed by EOSC; i.e., a provider and a service entity are described by a clear set of metadata (schema), which follows the Provider and Resource profiles (<https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation>), respectively. The Provider and Resource profiles are provided by the EOSC Portal onboarding team and define the set of

² <https://eosc-edmi.github.io/>

metadata needed for describing the services and the providers of research infrastructures and organizations which onboard the catalogue of the EOSC Portal.

Next, the NEANIAS data catalogue will be provided through Zenodo platform (<https://zenodo.org/>). Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema (<https://schema.datacite.org/>) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments. Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there. Both the service and data catalogues will support versioning. A globally unique and persistent ID (PID) will be assigned to every resource via Zenodo.

Accessible. The NEANIAS portal provides continuous access to the service and data catalogues via the web. The NEANIAS service catalogue also provides continuous access to the catalogue via standard APIs that are HTTP REST APIs. The description of the Service Model is documented in the API documentation page (<https://catalogue.neanias.eu/openapi>). The data catalogue will be provided through Zenodo platform. All metadata in Zenodo for individual records as well as record collections is harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. Data and metadata in Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository.

Interoperable. Each service collected in the NEANIAS service catalogue is stored in the Service Data Model as a separate XML/JSON file. For metadata interoperability, service schema will reuse terms from widely known vocabularies and ontologies such as the Dublin Core terms and Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS), including taxonomies and classifications for enumerated attributes of a service. Similarly, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. Interoperability will be supported by the provision of dedicated APIs that allow the import and export of the content in standard formats (XML, JSON) and standard data models.

Re-usable. The public content within the NEANIAS catalogue and services is available for download and re-use with no restrictions or embargo. The content will be available under permissive licenses, (CC-BY 4.0, CC-0 or comparable) but certain conditions (e.g. Noncommercial use=NC) and/or exceptions may also apply. The NEANIAS service catalogue is based on the FOSS [elInfraCentral](#) software which is available under the GPL/A license. In the cases where specific service information cannot be publicly shared, the reasons will be mentioned in their metadata descriptions (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related). In Zenodo, the code is open source, and built on the foundation of the Invenio digital library (<https://invenio-software.org/>) which is also open source. The work-in-progress, open issues, and roadmap are shared openly in GitHub. All meta data is openly available under CC0 license, and all open content is openly accessible through open APIs. License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an Open Definition license (<https://opendefinition.org/>). Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.

3.7.2. C2 core services

Most of C2 Services are infrastructure level services and are not directly handling data at the level to impose data FAIRness policies. C2 services shall be open to operate on all data policies that may be employed by higher level services, including those of selected business cases.

Nevertheless, services provided are able to support the FAIR principles applied by other core services, especially C1 services, as well as C3 and C4 and all thematic services. Mostly related to those are services that allow data depositing, transfer and sharing that allow carrying out NEANIAS policies related to the preservation and access to data.

3.7.3. C3 core services

As data is the main element in C3 AI services, and data is mostly handled by C1 services, FAIRness is supported indirectly through the policies of C1 core services.

As the result of machine learning algorithms, trained models are produced, which are served (C3.2), and models are also be made accessible for re-use purposes, such as transfer learning.

3.7.4. C4 core services

C4 Visualization services implement FAIR principles by employing open file formats and the use of metadata, including persistent identifiers, to describe the data thus making data findable and provides searchable metadata as well. In doing this, standards and recommendations from e.g. OGC and IVOA organizations (see Section 3.6 for more details) and C1 data services are being employed making data accessible for open-source tools and services to process the data.

3.8. Operation

The delivery and operation of the NEANIAS services adhere to the recommendations reported in Deliverable D7.1 [3] of NEANIAS, which stem from well-known and established practices as well as from preliminary results of a survey among the involved partners:

- service management processes follow the FitSM standards family, which aim at achievable IT service management;
- software implementation is supported by tools available to NEANIAS service developers and which allow automatic software building, testing and deployment, possibly using Continuous Integration and Delivery (CI/CD) workflows;
- software documentation has a single access point for all NEANIAS services and relies on the popular Read The Docs (readthedocs.org) document sharing environment;
- software, where applicable, should use free and open-source licenses and should be published to online code sharing platforms (such as GitHub);
- operational service-related issues and feedback from both NEANIAS internal sources and external users are collected through specific tools, already deployed as part of the activities of task T7.2;
- operational services are monitored, the related quality metrics are collected and, where applicable, automatically reported to the EOSC facilities;
- the development, delivery and operation of NEANIAS services can rely on the infrastructures operated by consortium members;
- paradigms such as high availability and Infrastructure as Code (IaC) should be adopted when designing, developing and operating the NEANIAS services.

3.9. Security

Security in NEANIAS is based of 3 elements:

- The **user**: the user is defined, authenticated, informed and granted various forms of access and has a central role in the definition and enforcement of security. Abstractions such as “groups” or “roles” may be present still referring to the user.
- The **service**: the service has the main responsibility of applying a security policy to resources that it manages (data, cpu, logic, storage, etc). This security policy is defined on a per service basis and is not unique per service. Yet NEANIAS project defines a set of policies that services will opt to follow for simplifying the interpretation of each service commitment.
- The **infrastructure**, that offers the glue among users and services. It translates, in a trustworthy manner, users, roles, groups into elements that can be consumed by services in order to apply their policies. It also supplies support to link users to those policies on a per resource basis.

3.9.1. NEANIAS AAI Concepts

In this section the infrastructure perspective is presented, and through this the representation of users and the instruments offered to services for application of their respective policies.

With respect to security, NEANIAS offers a horizontal solution that can be utilized by all the underlying NEANIAS services. This solution focuses on the aspects of Authentication and Authorization. Another important aspect that the security considerations can propose and facilitate alternative approaches is that of request delegation.

With respect to authentication, the identity federation paradigm (https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-federation-1_0.html#rfc.section.1) is used to facilitate the authentication and registration to the NEANIAS catalog of users, principals that are authenticated through external identity providers. Comprising the identity federation, the following cases can be identified:

- NEANIAS Single Sign On (SSO) – Users registered through the NEANIAS Consortium Single Sign On solution can be authenticated through the respective identity provider and are part of the user federation (<https://sso.neanias.eu/>)
- EOSC AAI – Users authenticated through the European open Science Cloud Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure (EOSC AAI) (<https://eosc-portal.eu/>) will also be authenticated to access the NEANIAS infrastructure. Through this identity federation scheme, users with access to a wide variety of identity providers gain access to the NEANIAS services. Some of these providers include:
 - EDUGain Access Check
 - EGI Check-In
 - B2Access
 - OpenAIRE
 - ORCID
- OpenID Connect Identity Providers – The authorization solution employed by NEANIAS is based on the OpenID Connect protocol (OIDC) (https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html). Identity providers that expose OIDC compatible endpoints can be registered and used to authenticate users

- Social platforms – In addition to all other identity providers, if required, widely used social providers such as Google, Microsoft, Facebook, Linked In, etc could be used to authenticate users
- Local users – Beyond external identity providers, the option to authenticate users through local user accounts is also available. It is expected that this method is primarily be used for maintenance and administration accounts

With respect to the supported grant flow through which the requestor identity is federated and subsequently propagated to servicing endpoints, the following mechanisms can be identified:

- Authorization Code Grant Flow (<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6749#page-24>) – This flow is usually the preferred method to authenticate users via Open Id Connect. In the first request, the user is redirected to the external identity provider where he is authenticated and then redirected back to the identity consumer site with an authorization code. Subsequently, another request is made to exchange the authorization code with a token set containing information such as access, refresh and id token. This flow is utilized to authenticate users through external identity providers.
- Client Credentials Grant Flow – This flow can be used for machine-to-machine authentication. In this grant, a specific user is not authorized but rather the credentials are verified and a generic access token is returned. This flow is utilized to authenticate NEANIAS services in order to interoperate with other NEANIAS services
- API Keys – This method is not part of the Open ID Connect specification and is not being centrally managed. It is rather an option for services that requires a simpler approach to authenticate client requests, whether these are within the NEANIAS ecosystem, or to external services.

The authentication flow that passes through the centrally managed NEANIAS AAI service exposing suitable user info endpoints (https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html#UserInfo), through which the respective id tokens can be used to retrieve the caller's claims. This information will be provided in the form of a JWT token (JSON Web Token) (<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc7519>), containing information to be utilized by servicing components.

With respect to authorization, the following alternatives can be made available and can be utilized based on specific service needs. It should be noted that these alternatives are not necessarily mutually exclusive, and a combination can be used by some service as seems most fitting.

- Role based – The mechanisms to define roles within the NEANIAS AAI Single Sign On (SSO) solution are provided. These roles can be subsequently assigned to authenticated users and the information flow down to services with each request as the respective caller claims. The roles can be defined with a global application scope, or they can be client specific. This way, each service can define a set of roles that do not clash in semantics with other service needs. In addition to roles, user groups can be employed and semantics on group membership can be utilized by the services or even be used as an administration utility to easily propagate affective roles to groups of users

- Resource based – A mechanism to define ad hoc resources within the NEANIAS AAI service can be investigated. The purpose of such a construct would be to allow NEANIAS services, through respective exposed API endpoints to autonomously define resources and manage user authorization over them. The scope of these resources can be determined in an ad hoc fashion by each service, although it is expected that coarse grain resources would be used
- Service Specific – it is expected that each service has diverse authorization requirements. For this reason, in addition to the Role and Resource based authorization that could be offered horizontally, each service could employ fine grained authorization policies within its own business logic. For this case, the horizontal NEANIAS solution would be limited to providing consistent client subject identifiers and any origin information it has available to facilitate in-service solutions, possibly, ranging from access control lists (ACL) to custom business rules

With respect to request delegation, the approach taken can be differentiated depending on the caller and recipient requirements. The initial recipient receiving a user request has all the tracking and identification information of the caller through the respective JWT token. In case this recipient requires, in the flow of normal execution, to invoke other services to complete or forward the service request, two cases can be distinguished:

- Service Identification – The underpinning service may only require that the caller service is authenticated, and any authorization checks are handled at the level of service requestor. Tracking and accounting actions are handled by the recipient at the level of caller service and further bindings with respect to the request originator is accounted by the caller
- User Identification – The underpinning service requires complete knowledge of the request originator to handle aspects of its operation such as accounting, authorization, and any other business logic rules.

Depending on the use case, different alternatives can be examined.

- Instead of requesting a new access token for a service-to-service authentication, services that need to delegate user information to other services can use the access token send from the user. In this case the initial access token requested by the user, should have access to all the scopes required to finish the initial as well as subsequent request
- When performing service-to-service communication, apart from the access token services can also include in the API invocation enough information on the user that they are acting on behalf of. This can be in the form of a direct API parameter or even through some request header. The receiving service must be aware of this header and able to propagate it to potential subsequent requests

In the latter case caution needs to be applied to make sure that the propagated information is not tampered with over untrusted network and unsecure communication channels. Countermeasures against this could include trusted networks, transfer level encryption as well as signing the propagated information through well-established standards (public-private key encryption and signing). To facilitate the full lifecycle of service development, the security environment can be sandboxed to differentiate between production, staging and

development environment. Different users and federation identity providers can be supported in each of the environment specific sandboxes (see Deliverable D7.5 [5]).

3.9.2. Policy

Security policy is applied on a per service basis. However, the following general policy shall be applied in NEANIAS:

- Each service presents a terms of use document where its precise policy regarding security is presented.
- Each service may opt to pick one of predefined data security policies that has been presented by the project.
- Services should clearly present to the user any risks for exposing data uploaded or utilized by the service to 3rd parties, defining those 3rd parties.
- Services should prevent unauthenticated access to their end-points, unless those endpoints are intended for public use, in which case the endpoints should employ throttling or another protective mechanism to prevent misuse of infrastructure resources and should avoid consuming substantial network, storage or network resources.
- Services should apply some mechanism to prevent unauthorized data access. The granularity this is applied should be evident to the provider of data.
- All services must avoid placing sensitive or otherwise protected data in their logs and accounting records, if this is not strictly required for performing their activity. Any such data use should be made evident to their user and get her consent.
- Services should avoid profiling of users unless necessary. In such case they should present the user with relevant information and need and get her consent.
- Services shall preserve user consent statements according to GDPR guidelines.
- Services shall preserve any sensitive information according to GDPR guidelines.

3.10. User Interfaces / User Experience

NEANIAS portal and services offer web-based graphical user interfaces to allow users to perform various actions. These interfaces are designed based on the basic principles of web design in order to offer users a frictionless and engaging user experience.

These basic principles include the following guidelines:

Usability: any design element of the user interface should have a purpose. A less-is-more approach could help emphasize simplicity as opposed to clutter.

Simplicity: simple language that is clear and concise should be used as it can be easily understood by different types of users and helps reduce ambiguity at the same time.

Consistency: the user interface should be consistent by making the visual presentation of the same type of information and behavior of the same interactive elements predictable, thus ensuring continuity of previously acquired knowledge.

Narrativity: users should be able to understand the relationship between specific actions and why they happen, what happens afterwards, and how that affects future events, all based on the flow of time.

Feedback: the user interface should have an interactive design that responds to user actions and encourages communication. For example, a clicked icon could change color or shape.

Intuitive and user-friendly interface: a friendly user interface should allow only for an appropriate set of actions and prevent situations that result in errors as for example warn users for actions where they might damage data. At the same time the use of familiar and recognizable concepts widely understood by all types of users could help users navigate more easily without having to follow a learning process.

Compatibility: the user interface should make use of technology widely available to users.

Responsiveness: the web design should be responsive in order to render well on a variety of devices and window or screen sizes used by different users.

Accessibility (optional): the user interface design should be usable by as many people as possible including people with disabilities.

Although NEANIAS user interfaces are implemented by different service providers using a variety of technologies, a general NEANIAS web toolkit has been offered with optional elements and guidelines to enable all services' user interfaces to have a similar and recognizable look and feel. This toolkit includes coloring guidelines, texts, html elements, proposals for menus, generic icons, possibly dynamic widgets and is analyzed in more detail in section 6.6.

3.11. Portability

NEANIAS service portability approach attempts to capture the existing landscape of services that are initially onboarded the project, their targeted evolution and the constraints that may underly those.

Implementation-wise, NEANIAS strongly suggests that services are implemented adopting portable technologies and rely on open standards for their interactions and dependencies so that they can be ported to different infrastructures. Furthermore, NEANIAS suggests that services are packaged in forms that can be ported across cloud infrastructures avoiding vendor lock-in. Examples of portable implementation technologies are java, python, .net core etc. while portable packaging technologies are war, jar, docker images etc.

Yet, service portability in NEANIAS may follow any of the following approaches, assuming that there are solid justifications to deviate from the optimal maximum portability case:

- **Portable Service:** A service that can be deployed in any major cloud infrastructure with minimal assumptions. Services may have preferences due to data/service locality exploitation patterns, however those are not technically limiting the deployment of the service in any other infrastructure that satisfies its limited restrictions of requirements.
- **Bound Service:** A service that is bound to an infrastructure or technology and needs to be deployed to it due to a number of reasons such as fixed local dependencies, security etc. (e.g. a service that requires internal access to a long-term storage tape facility, a specific version or flavor of operating system). Although bound to the infrastructure or technology the service is still a dynamic in terms of instantiation.

- **Fixed Service:** A fixed service is the most limited type of service as it is tightly bound with an infrastructure and/or technology and is expected to be a fixed point of reference with substantial static features. For instance, the servicing API of a large datastore is such a service, tightly bound to the technology and the physical resources that underlie the service.

Admittedly the boundaries among the three classes of service may not be sharp, however the classification greatly help service providers shape their service provisioning pattern.

3.12. Technology

The following technologies, frameworks and systems are used for the implementation of NEANIAS Core Services:

3.12.1. Programming languages

- Java: A general-purpose, object-oriented and strongly typed programming language. Along with other technologies that compose the Java Platform (e.g. the Java Virtual Machine), it is widely adopted for cross platform service implementation.
- C#: A multi-paradigm, object-oriented and strongly typed language developed by Microsoft. It is used worldwide for implementing desktop applications, web applications and web services.
- Python: An interpreted, loosely typed, general-purpose programming language. Its constructs and object-oriented approach aim to help programmers write clear, logical code for small and large-scale projects.
- JavaScript: An interpreted, prototype-based programming language specifically optimized for developing client applications.

3.12.2. Development frameworks

- .Net Core: A free open source, state-of-the-art framework for portable services implementation that builds upon the Microsoft .NET framework, enabling several computing languages, including C#. It was used for the implementation of several Core services.
- Angular: A widely adopted state of the art framework for cross browser web applications delivered under the SPA paradigm, building on the MVC design pattern for empowering structured, rich, client applications.
- NodeJS: An asynchronous event-driven JavaScript runtime, designed to build scalable network applications.
- Jupyter: An open-source project to support interactive data science and scientific computing across all programming languages.

3.12.3. Data Management frameworks

- ADAM: The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data. ADAM allows you extracting global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and long-term projections. Most of the data are updated daily to allow users having always the most recent data to play with.
- GeoServer: open-source server for managing, visualizing and sharing geospatial data.

- PostgreSQL: a powerful, open-source object-relational database system that uses and extends the SQL language combined with many features that safely store and scale the most complicated data workloads.
- CKAN: an open-source metadata and basic data management system to support data registration, discovery and sharing.

3.12.4. AI/ML frameworks

- Tensorflow: An open-source platform for machine learning; it provides a comprehensive, flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries and community resources that lets researchers push the state-of-the-art in ML.
- Keras: A high-level, open-source, neural networks API, written in Python and capable of running on top of different back-end platforms, among which Tensorflow; it is designed with a focus on enabling fast experimentation.
- Spark MLlib: a distributed machine-learning framework on top of Spark Core that, due in large part to the distributed memory-based Spark architecture, is faster than most disk-based implementations.
- DeepLearning4J: Eclipse Deeplearning4j is the first commercial-grade, open-source, distributed deep-learning library written for Java and Scala. Integrated with Hadoop and Apache Spark, DL4J brings AI to business environments for use on distributed GPUs and CPUs.
- Streamlit.io: an open-source app framework for Machine Learning and Data Science teams able to quickly turn python code into a dynamic web app.

3.12.5. Visualization Frameworks

- Dash: a productive Python framework for building web applications.
- Plotly: an interactive, [open-source](#) plotting library that supports over 40 unique chart types covering a wide range of statistical, financial, geographic, scientific, and 3-dimensional use-cases.
- VTK: open-source, freely available software system for 3D computer graphics, modeling, image processing, volume rendering, scientific visualization, and 2D plotting. It supports a wide variety of visualization algorithms and advanced modeling techniques, and it takes advantage of both threaded and distributed memory parallel processing for speed and scalability, respectively.

3.12.6. Major Background Systems

The following systems are utilized in the background as technologies in NEANIAS Core Services:

- OpenStack: a free open standard cloud computing platform, mostly deployed as infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) in both public and private clouds where virtual servers and other resources are made available to users. The platform consists of interrelated components that control diverse, multi-vendor hardware pools of processing, storage, and networking resources throughout a data center. Users either manage it through a web-based dashboard, through command-line tools, or through RESTful web services.
- Kubernetes: an open-source container-orchestration system for automating application deployment, scaling, and management.

- **ELK Stack:** a system including three open-source projects: Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana. Elasticsearch is a search and analytics engine. Logstash is a server-side data processing pipeline that ingests data from multiple sources simultaneously, transforms it, and then sends it to a "stash" like Elasticsearch. Kibana lets users visualize data with charts and graphs in Elasticsearch.
- **Docker:** a popular Linux-based containerization system, which allows to ship applications already bundled with their runtime dependencies.
- **Apache Spark:** An open-source distributed general-purpose cluster-computing framework. Spark provides an interface for programming entire clusters with implicit data parallelism and fault tolerance. In particular, it supports Spark MLlib, a distributed machine-learning framework that is employed by AI services.
- **Keycloak:** an open-source Identity and Access Management solution. It provides support for User Identity Federation and Single Sign On scenarios through widely used protocols such as Open ID Connect 1.0 and SAML 2.0.

4. System Architecture

In this section of the report the overall architectural perspective of NEANIAS is presented, in order to allow the reader to comprehend the full breadth and depth of services and capabilities to be offered by the arising services ecosystem.

At first, a diagrammatic overview of the ecosystem is given, in the form of logical layered architecture. Although the precise architectural approach is a mix of microservices and service layers, it is assumed that the layered visualization allows easier visualization of the concepts. To support the reader, brief descriptions of the elements presented in the diagrams are provided. Complementing the architecture, a reference service lifecycle is presented, so that the notion of a “NEANIAS service” emerges, as a piece of software that loosely conforms to some principles.

Through those two major diagrammatic and textual descriptions, one can comprehend the application of various principles of SOA, Open Science and EOSC architecture in general. One can also envisage how core services are brought together to yield reusable generic services and empower the thematic services delivered by the research sectors.

Finally, an indicative hypothetical physical architecture is introduced, in order to present concrete deployment options allowed by the presented architecture and its principles.

4.1. Architecture overview

NEANIAS architecture follows the distributed, n-tier architecture model. In this architecture NEANIAS Services are logical architecture blocks that cover specific functional or technological requirements of the infrastructure and are exposed to other NEANIAS or 3rd parties' services via their contracts. NEANIAS services themselves may, and usually are, composite multi-tier systems encapsulating microservices and protocols for their internal operation. In few cases those internal components may be robust, well defined and exposable on their own into the infrastructure, however they will not be presented as essential building block of the overall architecture presented here, so as to allow the document to focus on the notion of NEANIAS ecosystem of services.

NEANIAS services fall under 8 major groups, which can be logically clustered in 3 clusters

- **Base Core Services**, a cluster of generic services that provide basic tooling for NEANIAS ecosystem services.
 - **Open Science Lifecycle support services (C1)**
 - **EOSC hub Research infrastructures and cloud integration enabling services (C2)**
- **Advanced Core Services**, a cluster of services that build on base ones to deliver higher level generic yet focused in a specific domain services to be exploited by thematic services, which include:
 - **Artificial intelligence Services (C3)**
 - **Visualisation Services (C4)**
- **Thematic Services**, a cluster of services that includes top-level services for:
 - **Underwater research sector services (Ux)**, emerging from the requirements and work of WP2.

- **Atmospheric research sector services (Ax)**, emerging from the requirements and work of WP3.
- **Space research sector services (Sx)**, emerging from the requirements and work of WP4.
- **Business innovation sector Services**, i.e., services that may emerge to fulfill the business sector needs, which remain to be identified and designed in next stages of the project.

Although not strict, the diagram in Figure 1 coarsely depicts the stack of those service clusters and groups in NEANIAS.

Figure 1: Logical layering of NEANIAS service clusters

4.2. Logical architecture [CITE]

Figure 2 depicts the coarse logical architecture of NEANIAS.

In this diagram 5 layers of abstractions are depicted:

- Level 0: Physical resources of the infrastructure, such as compute, store, network, users etc.
- Level 1: Abstractions of physical resources, such as virtual machines, standard storage APIs, user identities etc.
- Level 2: Services that act close to resource abstractions and mainly orchestrate access to those resources adding higher level features.

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- Level 3: Services that provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering functional features, however they are mainly intended for composition of higher-level services rather than standalone ones.
- Level 4: Services that are targeting specific use cases. Might form applications (i.e. sets of services, usually with rich user interfaces that collectively serve some use) or standalone services that provide specific tools to their users.

Apart from those services, there are two sets of services that reside outside or at the boundaries of NEANIAS infrastructure:

- Boundary services, that are defined by NEANIAS, support the provisioning of NEANIAS services but may be residing on or be integrated in external infrastructures to offer their features.
- External services, that are provided by infrastructures not controlled by NEANIAS on their own terms and specifications.

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Figure 2: Logical architecture diagram

4.3. Fundamental building blocks

In the logical architecture presented in Figure 2, one can identify the following fundamental elements that define of NEANIAS service landscape:

- **NEANIAS Access Gate & Catalogue Portal:** The area where the user meets the NEANIAS service and data offerings. It offers general information on NEANIAS services as well as view of the service and access points to user-facing services.
- **Thematic Services:** Services focusing on offering solutions to challenges met by thematic sector communities in the three domains addressed by the project.
- **AI Service:** an umbrella service that encloses a number of technologies for Artificial Intelligence related tasks execution, which start from selection of algorithms, cover algorithm training and subsequently application in various tasks (e.g. prognosis) and feedback integration. The service will encapsulate training datasets.

- **Visualisation Service:** an umbrella service that encloses a number of technologies for visualizing and exploring specific data types. It may be coupled with specific clients that deliver the visualization the end-user.
- **High level infrastructure services:** Services that target the end user, from the stand point of the infrastructure:
 - **Service Catalogue:** A human accessible catalogue of service offerings of NEANIAS, compliant with the EOSC Portal directives, where users may locate project's service and data offerings.
 - **Notification Service:** A generic, multichannel, rule-based, notification service, for delivering important messages to users.
- **Data services and catalogues:**
 - **OpenDMP / Argos:** A service for managing and publishing Data Management Plans.
 - **Data Validation Service:** A service to allow users to validate data products.
 - **Data Exploration Service:** A set of components that allow users to interactively explore and handle data present in NEANIAS data space, or offered by services APIs.
 - **Research Product Catalogue:** A repository listing datasets of NEANIAS. Services may publish and retrieve dataset descriptions from the catalogue, and locate the endpoints where those datasets reside.
 - **Data Publishing Service:** A repository for depositing data produced by NEANIAS services.
 - **PID Service:** A service offering standard Persistent Identifiers for data sets produced by NEANIAS services.
 - **Data Sharing Service:** A set of components that allow users to share data on the infrastructure data space.
- **Infrastructure Support Services:**
 - **Configuration Management:** a distributed redundant service for storage of configuration information and secrets required by services instances to perform their operations.
 - **Service Instance Registry:** A machine accessible catalogue (accessible via REST APIs) to register and locate active service endpoints via their metadata, essential for supporting a dynamic SOA ecosystem.
 - **Accounting Service:** A set of components, rules and a service that collects, aggregates and presents accounting information from other NEANIAS services.
 - **Log Aggregation Service:** A set of components, rules and a service that allow the centralized gathering of logs coming from NEANIAS services, in order to facilitate infrastructure quality assessment.
 - **AuthN/AuthZ (AAI):** A gateway to Identity providers that are linked to NEANIAS and allows the authentication of local users. It also supports service authentication and provides fundamental instruments to support client authorization, yet NEANIAS services may opt for different means for the latter.
- **Persistent Storage Abstractions**
 - **Data-type specific stores:** Datastores specialized to manage data via services that comprehend the internal structure of the datasets. Such may be relational

- databases, geospatial data stores etc. Those are instantiated by other services and not generally available.
- **Long Term Store:** a backend storage abstraction that can be trusted for long term preservation of datasets. The service may be even offline, resulting in response times substantially inferior compared to other store technologies.
 - **Persistent Storage Abstractions:** Abstractions for management of infrastructure's persistent storage resources.
 - **Data Depositing Service:** A data storage abstraction a store to deposit data for (re)use. Data may be mostly deposited in object forms which in cases may even be not directly usable by users.
 - **Compute Management Abstractions:** Abstractions for management of infrastructure containers that may apply policies for optimizing the performance and resilience of the system, if services and infrastructure allow it. It provides specific CPU and memory abstractions.
 - **Container Service:** The main carrier of service executable elements. At least one is being defined by NEANIAS, but more may emerge in the course of the project, if compliant with infrastructures available.
 - **DAAS:** A service managing packaged executable elements deployment on Container Service.
 - **Fundamental abstractions:**
 - **Digital identity:** is the representation of a user in the virtual landscape.
 - **Cloud Platform Service (IaaS):** offers storage, network and computation resources to the infrastructure and its users.
 - **EOSC/eInfrastructures Services**
 - **EOSC AAI:** The AAI of EOSC which will be one of the main IdPs engaged by NEANIAS AAI.
 - **EOSC Compute:** An abstraction for computation offered by EOSC service marketplace, that may be utilized on demand by NEANIAS services. EGI compute may be one of those.
 - **EOSC Storage:** An abstraction for storage offered by EOSC, that may be utilized on demand by NEANIAS services. EUDAT B2Store is one example of such storage service.
 - **EOSC Accounting:** An accounting service gathering accounting data from EOSC services.
 - **EOSC Monitoring:** A monitoring service monitoring services offered under the EOSC marketplace.
 - **3rd Party IdP:** Identity Provider linked to NEANIAS AAI.
 - **3rd Party Data Catalogue:** Other catalogues, such as OpenAIRE etc. that may be linked to NEANIAS data catalogue, to draw dataset descriptions for further promotion of open science.
 - **EOSC Portal, Catalogue and Marketplace:** The component in EOSC Portal where all NEANIAS services are listed for discovery by researchers and scientists.

4.4. NEANIAS reference service

In Figure 3 an indicative lifecycle of a service starting up to serve its users in NEANIAS is presented. In this flow, the following steps may be present:

- Initialization: any work performed by the service before starting interaction with NEANIAS services. May refer to container handling, point 0 configuration application etc.
- Configuration discovery / access [Optional]: the service discovers the configuration options needed for its operation. Those might be drawn from local store (i.e. container defined) or from infrastructure services. Configuration may refer to default operation parameters, fixed dependency endpoints, secrets etc.
- Service dependency discovery [Optional]: the service may access the catalogue or other technologies in order to discover the services it depends on, in order to provide its features to its users. In this stage the access points of services that satisfy the requirements of the service are located.
- Data discovery [Optional]: the service may discover datasets that might be fundamental for its operation. Examples might be a training set of an AI service, or map terrain data for a mapping service.
- Store allocation [Optional]: in case the service will need pre-allocated store, at this point it checks to acquire it.
- Compute allocation [Optional]: in case the service will need some allocated computational power or memory size, it could ask for it before starting up.
- Data fetch: following store allocation, the service might request the access of data it needs to use in the allocated storage, which may incur some data moving activity.
- Process: when prerequisite data and relevant resources are ensured, the service may process those in order to initiate its servicing lifecycle. Processing may range from simple validation to calculation of complex structures that will allow the service to respond to its client's requests.
- Registration: At this point the service is ready to start responding to requests from clients, thus it registers itself to the instance registry, for others to be able to discover it.
- Listening / monitoring: The service is listening to client servicing requests, management requests (if supported) and monitoring requests.
- Un-registration: As a respond to a specific request posed by the hosting infrastructure or a privileged caller, the service unregisters itself
- Cleanup: The service cleans up any allocations it might have performed.

Figure 3: Reference service instantiation lifecycle

In Figure 4 an indicative lifecycle of a service serving a client request in NEANIAS is presented. There, one can identify the following steps:

- The client invokes the service.
- Authentication of the client is performed under one of the supported models.
- Initial authorization is performed, which filters out whether the specific client may be invoking the particular endpoint, potentially analyzing the parameters of the invocation in case a resource-dependent authorization model is supported by the service (e.g., ACLs)

- In case additional configuration needs to be discovered at this point the service accesses either local or central configuration. One example could be the access to specific secrets due to specific users invoking the service etc.
- Late service discovery may take place at this point for services that may need to react to a fast-changing environment. However, this should take into account that the active discovery cost needs to be justified to the caller.
- Depending on the request, the service may need to locate and access specific data. Those may be explicitly or implicitly defined by the caller, or the service may be acting on dynamically located data that need to be sought for.
- The service may need storage to move discovered data or data to be generated. Such storage may need to be allocated, or ensured at this point, before data fetch or generation is initiated.
- If data need to be fetched close to the service, then those are transferred at this point. The process may be an asynchronous or incremental one, changing substantially the service lifecycle, according to its design needs.
- Similarly, the service may depend on computational power or memory that need to be allocated in the local or other infrastructures.
- Once all resources are present the service may invoke a processing cycle which may generate new data or prepare existing data for exploration.
- Data generation although not technically separate from processing is a “semantic stage” when new data are generated by a process.
- Persistence may follow data generation stage, if those data may serve further uses. Persistence may take place in mid/long term service storage areas of the project, i.e. escape the local storage of a virtual node.
- Exploration of data, via a service specific approach, may follow any of the previous optional stages, i.e., processing, generation or persistence.
- Last step may be the publication of data to catalogues and public data repositories.

Figure 4: Reference servicing lifecycle

4.5. Physical architecture

In Figure 5, a potential deployment scenario for NEANIAS services is presented.

Figure 5: Hypothetical deployment of NEANIAS services

In the presented physical architecture scenario, the following assumptions are made:

1. A core infrastructure provider for NEANIAS is present, hosting services:
 - a. NEANIAS Gateway
 - b. NEANIAS AAI
 - c. Service Instance Registry
 - d. Data Catalogue
 - e. Service Catalogue
 - f. Storage Services (group of services)
 - g. Computation Services (group of services)
 - h. A portable Thematic Service Z that depends on storage and computation offered by the infrastructure provider.
2. OpenAIRE is present with two services.

- a. The OpenAIRE catalogue, that harvests metadata from NEANIAS Data Catalogue, following the validation of the service and the compliance with OAI-PMH protocol.
 - b. The Zenodo repository that is hosting data (and metadata) pushed to it by services, which is directly utilized by Thematic Service X of the scenario.
3. EOSC is present with 3 services:
 - a. The EOSC Service Catalogue, which includes information from NEANIAS Service Catalogue
 - b. The EOSC Computation Services (offered by a 3rd party) that is used by Thematic Service X
 - c. EOSC AAI service that is linked to NEANIAS AAI.
4. A NEANIAS Large Data Provider, which hosts a large data volume that may be infeasible to be moved for practical reasons, or a data volume that is locked behind access policies, that hosts:
 - a. Local storage exposed via protocols that match the data type managed and facilities offered on top of those. Those data themselves may be well a portion or replica of data present in another infrastructure (External RI C).
 - b. Local computation services, that allow computation to run next to data.
 - c. Thematic Service Y, which is a service bound to the data and computation services of NEANIAS Large Data Provider.
5. An External Research Infrastructure C that hosts primary or replicas of primary observation / modeling data, which usually consists of petabytes of digital objects in sector specific formats.
6. A NEANIAS X service provider, that offers:
 - a. minimal local computational capacity to instantiate its service X
 - b. Thematic Service X, which is mostly relying on external EOSC provided computational resources (e.g. EGI) to deliver is computation bound results and data storage services provided by OpenAIRE offered Repository.
7. A NEANIAS Cloud Provider B that hosts
 - a. Core Service B, which depends on data managed by the NEANIAS Core Infrastructure Provider.
 - b. Local computation to allow execution of Core Service B.

5. Fundamental resource abstractions in NEANIAS

5.1. Storage

The infrastructures employed by the NEANIAS services provide storage resources through several abstractions.

OpenStack based infrastructures such as the GARR Cloud and the MTA SZTAKI Cloud provide *volumes*, which are raw unformatted virtual block devices. These can be attached to a virtual machine instance and used as hard drives by the instance's operating system. Moreover, volumes allow the creation of *snapshots*, i.e. read-only point-in-time copies of a volume's contents. Volumes on the GARR Cloud and the MTA SZTAKI Cloud rely on Ceph, a distributed and fault-tolerant data storage platform.

OpenStack based infrastructures also provide *images*, which are immutable, read only storage abstractions, used to provide the operating system installation during the creation of virtual machines.

Another type of storage employed by NEANIAS services is the object store provided by Cloud infrastructures. The GARR Cloud provides an S3 compatible RESTful API to manage *objects* and *object containers*, which are abstractions for files and directories. Also, the object store is backed by Ceph³, to provide data redundancy and fault tolerance.

For Kubernetes clusters, such as the GARR Container Platform, the main storage abstraction are *storage classes*, *persistent volumes* and *persistent volume claims*. A storage class abstracts the different "classes" of storage available on the cluster, which may be associated to different quality-of-service levels or backup policies. A persistent volume is a piece of storage in the cluster that has been provisioned statically or dynamically through storage classes. A persistent volume claim is instead a request of storage by a user, with a specific size and access mode.

Finally, the NEANIAS data sharing core service, based on NextCloud, also provides storage to NEANIAS services. The service providers can mount storage in the form of a remote filesystem leveraging the WebDav protocol.

Figure 6 summarizes the abstraction layers here described.

³ <https://ceph.io/>

Figure 6: Layering of the storage resource abstractions leveraged by NEANIAS

5.2. Computation

OpenStack based infrastructures, such as the GARR Cloud and the MTA Cloud provide computational resources as *virtual machine instances*, leveraging hypervisor technologies and abstracting available CPU (vCPUs) and memory resources.

Inside virtual machine instances, *containers* are employed by some NEANIAS services. Containers are operating system and computational resources abstractions, and can be implemented by several technologies, namely Docker and LXC.

In Kubernetes based clusters, such as the GARR Container Platform, computational resources (including GPUs) are abstracted through *Pods*, which are groups of Docker containers sharing the same networking stack, and which can be deployed on “workers”, i.e. server abstractions. Kubernetes provides also deployment abstractions, which allow to scale and upgrade pods.

Moreover, the GARR Container Platform allows the easy deployment of Jupyter Notebooks through the Helm package manager.

Figure 7 summarizes the relationship between the main computational abstractions employed in NEANIAS.

Figure 7: The computational resource abstractions leveraged by NEANIAS

5.3. Other resources

OpenStack based infrastructures, such as the MTA Cloud and the GARR Cloud provide abstraction for network components in the form of *virtual networks*, *floating IP addresses*, *virtual routers*, *security groups*, *load balancers* and more. Virtual machine instances created by the users are provided with internal private IP addresses and have the ability to map external public IP addresses (i.e., floating IPs) to instances, allowing, together with security groups (i.e. collections of firewall rules), external access to applications residing in OpenStack virtual machine instances.

In OpenStack resources are assigned to *projects*, to which many *users* can be added with a *role* (e.g., Member or Admin).

In Kubernetes, resources are instead grouped into *namespaces*. Moreover, Kubernetes provides the *service* abstraction (a way to expose an application as a network service) and the *ingress* abstraction (a highly customizable reverse proxy abstraction).

6. C1 Open-Science lifecycle support services & Components

C1 services, the Open Science lifecycle support services, enable the integration of NEANIAS thematic services with EOSC ecosystem and offer providers, services and users the ability to publish, present and locate resources.

In these section C1 services are described. First, the role of C1 services is briefly outlined and then each service is presented based on the Service Description template guidelines of the project.

6.1. The role of C1 services in NEANIAS

C1 services provide the necessary tools for NEANIAS services to be discoverable and accessible and integrated with EOSC Core system. The NEANIAS service catalogue portal and APIs are based on the eInfraCentral⁴ catalogue software, and enables NEANIAS service providers to register and present their services in a single project’s catalogue, which is compliant with the guidelines of EOSC. Through the NEANIAS portal and service catalogue users are able to browse, search and discover all thematic and core services available.

The NEANIAS data catalogue will be built on top of Zenodo Data repository service and will enable providers to publish their data as well as assign PIDs for digital assets making them unambiguously cited and therefore uniquely discoverable.

As part of the NEANIAS C1 services, providers are also being able to have access to common UI\UX elements for the presentation of their services and the development of uniform user journeys for all services that are developed in the context of NEANIAS. Finally, the providers will be able to create and maintain actionable Data Management Plans with the use of the Argos service provided by OpenAIRE.

6.2. NEANIAS Access Gate & Catalogue Portal

Short Name	Catalogue Portal (C1.1)	Lead partner	ATHENA
Type	UI web app	Contributors	-
Title	NEANIAS Catalogue Portal		
Service category	Open-Science lifecycle support services		
Description	NEANIAS catalogue portal offers to users a single-entry point to all NEANIAS list of services, including core, thematic services as well as datasets and other resources. The catalogue portal offers functionality for users to <i>browse</i> the available services, <i>search and filter</i> along EOSC compliant classification, such scientific domain or category a service is most relevant to, the maturity of the service, the intended use, etc., as well as to compare NEANIAS service offerings.		

Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

Documentation	N\A		
Service Endpoint	https://catalogue.neanias.eu/		
Source Code	Catalogue basis: https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue Service packaging for NEANIAS is available at https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c1-services/catalogue-service		
Technical details	Web portal built with AngularJS. Usage Analytics are collected in Matomo ⁵ . It integrates with NEANIAS AAI for authentication and it communicates with the catalogue service (c1.2) with REST API.		
Core integration	It needs the following integration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication / Authorization for authenticated users to login and update service metadata. • Logging is needed for web analytics. Matomo FOSS is used for this reason. • It is already integrated (via REST API with Catalogue service C1.2) 		
Depends on	Catalogue service C1.2 NEANIAS AAI		
Use cases	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> End users access the catalogue to find, access and browse services, datasets and other NEANIAS research resources NEANIAS service providers access the catalogue to add and update service metadata. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Start TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	NKUA \ ATHENA RC	License	GNU\GPL
Current Status	Production and Beta deployment. Extended with Web UI\UX functionality for a) adjusting to NEANIAS common UI templates, b) Connecting to NEANIAS AAI, c) addressing NEANIAS service providers' needs for service classification and management at the UI, d) UI support for the EOSC model (EOSC Profiles). NEANIAS Services mapped to EOSC profiles and populated the catalogue.		
Future Plans	EOSC integration for updating EOSC-onboarded services Integration with ticketing system and improvements. Accommodate changes \ new additions in EOSC Profiles (the description of providers and services) posed by EOSC portal		

6.3. NEANIAS Service Catalogue API

Short Name	Catalogue Service (C1.2)	Lead partner	ATHENA
Type	Web service (REST API)	Contributors	-
Title	NEANIAS Catalogue Service		
Service category	Open-Science lifecycle support services		

⁵ <https://matomo.org/>

Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

Description	NEANIAS catalogue service will offer the necessary service catalogue REST APIs for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. NEANIAS service providers to register and update the service metadata in the NEANIAS catalogue of services as well as monitor the usage (e.g., pageviews) regarding their services. b. 3rd party systems including EOSC portal to synchronize the service metadata with the service catalogue of NEANIAS. 		
Documentation	https://catalogue.neanias.eu/openapi		
Service Endpoint	https://catalogue.neanias.eu/developers		
Source Code	Catalogue basis: https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue Service packaging for NEANIAS is available at https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c1-services/catalogue-service		
Technical details	Web service built JAVAEE and PostgreSQL offering a list of REST methods for managing a catalogue of EOSC compliant services. Based on the eInfraCentral FOSS https://github.com/eInfraCentral , https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue		
Core integration	It covers the following integration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication / Authorisation for authenticated users to login and update service metadata. 		
Depends on	NEANIAS AAI		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. NEANIAS service providers use APIs to programmatically update the catalogue and also to publish services into EOSC • 3rd party systems may use the APIs to access the content of the catalogue 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	NKUA \ ATHENA RC	License	GNU\GPL
Current Status	Production and Beta deployment. Extended with functionality for a) addressing NEANIAS service providers' needs for service classification and management, b) new EOSC model for service metadata (EOSC Profiles). NEANIAS Services mapped to EOSC profiles and populated the catalogue.		
Future Plans	EOSC integration for updating EOSC-onboarded services Issue fixing and improvements. Accommodate any changes in EOSC Profiles (the description of providers and services) posed by EOSC portal		

6.4. NEANIAS Research Product Catalogue

This core service uses Zenodo; a data and document research repository offered via OpenAIRE in the EOSC catalogue of services. The table below presents how Zenodo is adopted to offer the functionality of the NEANIAS product catalogue core service.

Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

Short Name	RPC	Lead partner	
Type	UI Web App / Web Service	Contributors	
Title	NEANIAS Research Product Catalogue		
Service Category	Data Management		
Description	<p>The NEANIAS Research Product Catalogue (RPC) is the service that will store all products of the NEANIAS project, along with datasets that the users of the NEANIAS services which will make available online.</p> <p>Research products of the NEANIAS project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications • Software • Datasets used as input to NEANIAS services • Datasets produced by the NEANIAS services that the users wish to make available to others 		
Documentation	https://developers.zenodo.org		
Service Endpoint	https://zenodo.org		
Source Code	https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo		
Technical details	<p>For the research product catalogue, the NEANIAS project will use the OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform. Zenodo is an open data repository provided by CERN. In their own words: "Zenodo is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, Zenodo makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term." (https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide).</p> <p>We also created a NEANIAS community in Zenodo, so that all published datasets are grouped under this community. Zenodo supports basic metadata attributes (Dublin Core, see https://dublincore.org/) necessary to create a "record", i.e. an entry in the metadata repository of Zenodo. It also supports some extra metadata attributes, specific to certain record types. For example, a journal publication record may contain the volume number. Each published upload should contain a DOI (persistent identifier), thus Zenodo assigns a DOI to each upload, if not provided by the user. Finally, Zenodo offers a REST search API for the user's own records (https://developers.zenodo.org/#rest-api), and also harvesting functionality through the OAI-PMH protocol (https://developers.zenodo.org/#oai-pmh).</p>		
Core integration			
Depends on	None		
Use cases			

 Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

EOSC Service	Already an EOSC service		
Current TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR		License	GPL-2.0
Current Status	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.		
Future Plans			

6.5. Data Validation Service

Short Name	DVS	Lead partner	CITE, NKUA
Type	Web service / Web app	Contributors	
Title	NEANIAS Data Validation Service		
Service category	Data Management		
Description	<p>The Data Validation Service (DVS) is a service used by the NEANIAS thematic services (and via them, by their end-users) to rate (grade) the datasets they use and obtain the ratings of datasets. The identifier of a dataset is its DOI. This service has an administrative interface that allows its administrators to define the dimensions for the rating and view all registered ratings.</p> <p>Additionally, this service is accessible by the thematic NEANIAS services via a REST API, allowing the calling services to create new dimensions for rating, to register ratings for datasets, and to obtain aggregate ratings for datasets.</p> <p>Finally, we will investigate the potential for automatic rating of datasets, wherever this is possible, after consulting with the corresponding users of each dataset format.</p>		
Documentation	Not available yet		
Service Endpoint	Not available yet		
Source Code	Not available yet		
Technical details	The service will provide a web UI for initialization, and for assisting in technical support. Its main usage is via its REST API. Consuming services will need to authenticate themselves first, and also pass along the authenticated end-user credentials that DVS will verify.		
Core integration	It needs the following integration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication service, to identify the logged in user. • Service instance registry, to register itself. 		
Depends on	-		

Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A service creates a new “dimension” (subject) for rating datasets. • A service retrieves all registered dimensions. • A service registers a new rating for a dataset. • A service retrieves the aggregate rating of a dataset. • Support personnel logs in the UI of the service to view all registered ratings and response to support requests. 		
EOSC services integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eventually, EOSC AAI - (Optional) EOSC portal, if service is deemed publishable 		
EOSC Service	Potentially		
Start TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	CITE	License	FOSS (EURL or similar)
Availability	The service has not been deployed. Initial validation dealt with metadata for publishing datasets. Re-design has been completed and core elements have been selected. Integration / implementation will start after M18.		
Future plans	At MS6 a first version deployed with a local database, REST interface only, provided to support integration with other services. Eventually both Web UI and REST interfaces will be deployed and become operational, without automated rating. If automated rating proves viable, it will be experimented with		

6.6. Common User Interface Components

Short Name	NEANIAS web toolkit	Lead partner	CITE
Type	UI Component	Contributors	INAF
Title	NEANIAS web UI toolkit and template		
Service category	Open Science Lifecycle support components		
Description	A template for all services UI to be reused by all partners exposing UIs in the context of NEANIAS (look-and-feel, logo, CSS, menus, etc.)		
Technical details	NEANIAS spans UIs from several independent service providers. Those may be implemented in different technologies however their web aspect, wherever present, will be utilizing standard technologies, such as HTML5/JS/CSS. NEANIAS web toolkit offer optional elements and guidelines for all other services' web UIs to adopt in order to homogenize their look, and if possible, feel. The toolkit includes coloring guidelines, texts,		

 Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

	<p>html elements, proposals for menus, generic icons and, if needed, widgets for consistently exposing some backend services features.</p> <p>The components are based on existing mature web technologies, restyled and adapted to NEANIAS needs.</p>		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c1-web-toolkit/en/latest/		
Source Code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thematic landing page UI template: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c1-services/common-ui-components - Service UI components: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c1-services/common-services-ui-template 		
Core integration	<p>No general core integration is foreseen. Independent components may opt to communicate with specific backend services.</p>		
Depends on	None		
Use cases	<p>The toolkit elements are usable by all users interacting with NEANIAS services via their web interfaces. However, their exploitation is targeted for service UI implementers. Examples of supported cases are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adopt the color guidelines for the NEANIAS service UI. - Include a common area for project information and NEANIAS gateway exploration. - Adopt a specific set of icons for use by service UI. - Adopt a generic menu behavior and style. 		
EOSC Service	NO		
CURRENT TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR	CITE, INAF	License	FOSS (MIT, Apache or other similar)
Current status	<p>Generic stylesheet and color guidelines for thematic landing pages (see e.g., implementation for the SPACE sector: https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/ and ATMO-FLUD service: https://atmo-flud.neanias.eu/). Menu templates and button templates.</p>		
Future Plans	Specific components for service exposure as and when requested.		

6.7. OpenDMP / Argos

Short Name	OpenDMP	Lead partner	CITE
Type	UI Web App / Web Service	Contributors	ATHENA, OpenAIRE

 Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

Title	OpenDMP Software		
Service Category	C1 - Open Science		
Description	<p>OpenDMP is a software system that allows researchers to create and distribute interoperable, actionable Data Management Plans. The service is provided by OpenAIRE as Argos. NEANIAS contributes with a specific use case, validation and fixing of issues met during this use case. One of the cases contributed by NEANIAS is the evolution of system to follow the the RDA maDMP standard.</p>		
Documentation	Open DMP - User Guide (openaire.eu)		
Service Endpoint	Argos (on openaire.eu infrastructure)		
Source Code	dmp / OpenAIRE-EUDAT-DMP-service-pilot · GitLab		
Technical details	<p>Argos is a full REST API backend system, that operates on cloud infrastructures. On top of it resides an SPA (single page application) front end that manages the API. It utilizes common standards for consuming and integrating with external services (OpenID, SAML2, REST JSON APIs etc) and produces standards-based outcomes (maDMP).</p>		
Core integration	OpenDMP may integrate NEANIAS AAI. Yet supported deployment will be using EOSC AAI directly.		
Depends on	OpenDMP does not depend on other NEANIAS services.		
Use cases	NEANIAS researchers collaborate on the creation of Data Management Plans on OpenDMP.		
EOSC services integration	<p>OpenDMP may integrate with</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EOSC AAI - EOSC PID services (Zenodo etc) - EOSC repositories (Zenodo etc) - OpenAIRE indexing services 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR	OpenAIRE	License	FOSS (MIT, Apache or similar)
Current Status	<p>Public release to accommodating observations of NEANIAS users. Deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos.</p> <p>Integration with EOSC AAI has been implemented, however it is not enabled in the OpenAIRE deployment. As such users cannot hop from any NEANIAS service onto Argos directly, and this is scheduled for MS6. Integration with Zenodo (set for MS6) is provided by Argos.</p>		

Future plans	Updated user functionality (template management) and AAI integration (NEANIAS / Argos).
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6.8. Data Publishing Service

This core service uses Zenodo; a data and document research repository offered via Openaire in the EOSC catalogue of services. The table below presents how Zenodo is adopted to offer the functionality of the Neanias data publishing core service.

Short Name	DPS	Lead partner	CITE
Type	UI Web App / Web Service	Contributors	ATHENA
Title	Data Publishing Service		
Service Category	Data Management		
Description	The NEANIAS Data Publishing service is responsible for making research products available to the public. For the Data Publishing Service (DPS) NEANIAS will use the OpenAIRE's Zenodo platform (https://zenodo.org/).		
Documentation	https://developers.zenodo.org		
Service Endpoint	https://zenodo.org		
Source Code	https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo		
Technical details	<p>When creating a Zenodo "record", a user may upload the research product (e.g., a dataset) to the platform. While the metadata of a record is open to allow harvesting via the OAI-PMH protocol, the data may be:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. open under Creative Commons licensing, 2. embargoed under Creative Commons licensing, 3. restricted with per request access, 4. closed. <p>To support the case where a user aims to keep the data of the research product in a private repository, while still making its existence public via the Research Product Catalogue, we also propose the following convention. The user creates a Zenodo upload providing all necessary metadata and uploads a single JSON file with two data fields: a URL and a SHA256 hash of the file's contents. This way, metadata are searchable via the Zenodo platform, but the data remains private, possibly inside the NEANIAS Data Depositing Service. When a user wants to access this dataset, after being authorized via the Data Sharing Service, the consuming service can retrieve the URL from the</p>		

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	<p>metadata repository and verify the data is still intact, by comparing the hash of the data with the published one.</p> <p>We also created a “NEANIAS” community at Zenodo and instructed all service providers to ensure that all datasets published via their services should be registered in this community.</p>		
Core integration			
Depends on	None		
Use cases			
EOSC Service	Already an EOSC service		
Current TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR		License	GPL-2.0
Current Status	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.		
Future Plans	<p>When we presented Zenodo and its REST API to the service providers of the NEANIAS thematic services, we got the following feedback. Even though Zenodo allows one to use this API to upload a “record” (in Zenodo terminology), this record appears owned by whoever posted it, which in our case would be the service provider’s account at Zenodo. However, the actual owner of the record should be the end-user and not the service, as the end-user should be able to manage the record for its lifetime, after the initial upload (e.g., modify it to her own will). We investigated with Zenodo and they don’t support a “transfer of ownership” functionality.</p> <p>Because of issue above (in Current Status), we are currently investigating the feasibility of producing a (core) service that will take the dataset and its metadata from the thematic service, allow the end-user to sign-on to Zenodo with her own credentials, and then upload said dataset under her own name. We will report in a refresh of this deliverable on the progress of this exercise</p>		

6.9. Persistent Identifier Service

This core service uses Zenodo; a data and document research repository offered via Openaire in the EOSC catalogue of services. The table below presents how Zenodo is adopted to offer the functionality of the NEANIAS PID core service.

Short Name	PID	Lead partner	CITE
Type	UI Web App / Web Service	Contributors	ATHENA
Title	Persistent Identifier Service		
Service Category	Data Management		

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Description	The NEANIAS Persistent Identifier Service will enable the generation of PIDs for digital assets. The goal of this service is to make NEANIAS digital assets citable and thus discoverable. The service will be integrated with all NEANIAS services. The NEANIAS PID Service will be provided by OpenAIRE's Zenodo open access repository (https://zenodo.org/).		
Documentation	https://developers.zenodo.org		
Service Endpoint	https://zenodo.org		
Source Code	https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo		
Technical details	Zenodo offers a list of REST methods to upload and publish research outputs assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to those outputs if they do not have one already. As already described in paragraphs 5.3 and 5.8, all NEANIAS research and data outputs will be published in Zenodo and thus be assigned a DOI that will allow them to be easily and unambiguously cited.		
Core integration			
Depends on	None		
Use cases			
EOSC Service	Already an EOSC service		
Current TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR		License	GPL-2.0
Current Status	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.		
Future Plans			

7. C2 EOSC hub, RIs and cloud integration enabling services

C2 services, often called “Infrastructure enabling services “, or “enabling” services in the context of NEANIAS, form the lower level of services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and are the ones that deliver access to various levels of resources that serve the use cases of the project. In this section C2 group of services is presented. Following the brief presentation of their, each service is presented in alignment with the Service Description template adopted by the project.

7.1. The role of C2 services in NEANIAS

C2 cluster of services encloses a set of loosely coupled elements that enable the assembly of a virtual infrastructure to serve other services, bringing closer to them resources and processes EOSC hub, other Research and Cloud Computing Infrastructures. C2 services, along with physical infrastructures and low-level resource abstractions, form the NEANIAS virtual infrastructure fabric, upon which all other services build.

C2 services make heavy use of existing services and software, launching off from a high TRL, and are re-engineered in order to adapt to the NEANIAS and EOSC information and service model. In few cases service software is already present yet adaptation of its data models and/or configuration is required in order to serve NEANIAS needs.

As a general observation C2 services are not expected to be exposed as end-user services in EOSC Marketplace, however quite a few offers valuable toolkits for other infrastructures to build upon, thus they will be openly shared with others, both in the form of services as well as free and open-source software.

Note: C2 service range has substantially been extended compared to DoA presented ones, in order to respond to practical challenges raised by other services requirements and infrastructures’ integration needs.

7.2. NEANIAS AAI

Short Name	NEANIAS AAI	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Web service / UI web app	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure Service		
Service Category	C2 – Infrastructure Enabling		
Description	The NEANIAS AAI service offers a horizontal solution for all NEANIAS services to cover the common requirements of authenticated access, whether these come in the form of direct user requests or as cross service invocations. Furthermore, provisions to support some degree of the authorization of these requests are offered. The solution is based on widely accepted protocols and standards to ensure wide applicability of the approach.		

	<p>The NEANIAS AAI Service will eventually integrate with the respective EOSC AAI service and act as an Identity Consumer. Users registered and trusted by the EOSC AAI will be authenticated by the respective NEANIAS AAI service.</p>
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/aai-service/en/latest/
Service Endpoint	https://sso.neanias.eu/
Source Code	<p>KeyCloak basis: https://github.com/keycloak/keycloak Service packaging for NEANIAS is available at https://gitlab.neanias.eu/aai-service/server</p>
Technical details	<p>The NEANIAS AAI Service is backed by the Open Source Keycloak (keycloak.org) software. The software consists of a set of web API accessible endpoints to complete the needed authentication protocol interactions, as well as a set of web graphical user interfaces to support login, profile managements and administrative operations.</p> <p>To support the full lifetime of a service, three realms is set up to cover authentication and authorization needs for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development • Staging • Production <p>At each one of these realms, different external identity providers can be supported depending on needs.</p> <p>With respect to Authentication, the identity federation paradigm (https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-federation-1_0.html#rfc.section.1) is used to facilitate the authentication and registration to the NEANIAS catalog of users, principals that are authenticated through external identity providers. Comprising the identity federation, the following cases can be identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEANIAS Single Sign On (SSO) • EOSC AAI • eduGAIN • OpenID Connect Identity Providers • Social platforms • Local users <p>For further information one IdPs supported, one may refer to D6.1 [1].</p> <p>With respect to the supported grant flow through which the requestor identity is federated and subsequently propagated to servicing endpoints, the following grant flows will be supported:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authorization Code Grant Flow (https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6749#page-24). • Client Credentials Grant • For further information on grant flows, one may refer to D6.1. <p>The authentication flow that passes through the centrally managed NEANIAS AAI service exposes suitable user info endpoints (https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html#UserInfo), through which the respective id tokens can be used to retrieve the caller's claims. This information is provided in the form of a JWT token (JSON Web Token) (https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc7519) containing information to be utilized by servicing components.</p> <p>With respect to authorization, the following alternatives are offered through the NEANIAS AAI Service. It should be noted that these alternatives are not necessarily mutually exclusive, and a combination can be used by some service as seems most fitting.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role based. • Service Specific. <p>For further information on authorization options, one may refer to D6.1.</p>		
Core integration	<p>The NEANIAS AAI Service integrates with a set of other core services to facilitate primarily monitoring and accounting of its usage. Integration with these services is in loose form, making this integration optional, in setups that do not require such functionality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting – Accounting information on users registered, logins, user organization provenance, etc. - Logging – Logging information on low level troubleshooting as well as higher level action auditing 		
Depends on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - External IdPs (optional) 		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A NEANIAS service interact with the service to obtain user identification information - A NEANIAS service interacts with the service to obtain authorization assertions for a specific user 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR	CITE / 3 rd parties	License	Apache 2.0
Current Status	Production realm, dev and staging are made available. Integration with NEANIAS Logging and NEANIAS Accounting services has been		

	made available. Integration with NEANIAS Logging and NEANIAS Accounting services has been made available. Extensions for delivery of user information to services have been implemented.
Future Plans	<p>EOSC AAI integration will be enabled. Enhancements on the integration with the NEANIAS Accounting Service. Alpha availability of fine-grained resource level authorization will be evaluated.</p> <p>Additional targets of self-management and application of central token issuing for services will be considered depending on additional resources to be made available.</p> <p>In final version further authorization capabilities will be considered.</p>

7.3. Configuration Management Service

Short Name	NEANIAS Configuration Service	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Software library / Web service / UI web app	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Configuration Management Service		
Service Category	C2 – Infrastructure Enabling		
Description	The NEANIAS Configuration Management Service will provide a key value storage for storing configurations that will be used by NEANIAS's services. Configurations will be created or updated using an HTTP API that will be available.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/configuration-service/en/latest/		
Service Endpoint	configuration2.neanias.eu:2281 configuration1.neanias.eu:2281 configuration3.neanias.eu:2281 configuration.dev.neanias.eu:2281		
Source Code	Backed by apache zookeeper at https://github.com/apache/zookeeper Packaged / integrated for NEANIAS: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/configuration-service/server		
Technical details	The NEANIAS Configuration Management Service is backed by a distributed, highly available system. The storage will be replicated across multiple nodes of the service to guarantee data redundancy. NEANIAS Configuration Management		

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	<p>Service will operate as a key / value store. Data will be stored using a unique key and will be accessed using the same key.</p> <p>Restricted access is offered via ACLs in order to limit the actions (read/write) clients can perform.</p> <p>The main interface to NEANIAS Configuration Management Service offers API for utilization to its clients. All requests require authentication. The API is able to perform updates to specific keys. Multi-key updates use a transactional mechanism.</p> <p>NEANIAS Configuration Management Service provides a command-line user interface for administrator to easily review and monitor the usage of the service.</p>		
Core integration	<p>The NEANIAS Configuration Management Service will integrate with a set of other core services to facilitate primarily monitoring and accounting of its usage. Integration with these services will be in a decoupled form, making this integration optional in setups that do not require such functionality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting – Accounting information on storage usage, etc. (optional) - Logging – Logging information on low level troubleshooting as well as higher level action auditing 		
Depends on	-		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A NEANIAS service contacts the configuration management service in order to detect base configuration information, such as: the endpoint and database name to connect to and the accounts to use to access it. - A NEANIAS service contacts the configuration management service in order to detect the model of operation it applies 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	CITE	License	Apache 2.0
Current Status	Initial service delivery dependable for services to store and retrieve public configuration. Deployed in infrastructure.		
Future Plans	Major service update. Integration with logging / accounting.		

7.4. Service Instance Registry

Short Name	NEANIAS Service Registry	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Software library / Web service / UI web app	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Service Instance Registry		
Service Category	C2 – Infrastructure Enabling		
Description	<p>The NEANIAS Service Instance Registry will provide a list of all NEANIAS services among with information regarding their location and health status. NEANIAS's Services will be registered dynamically, creating list of all available services and their instances. Service Discovery API is available to provide real-time list of services, their location, and their health.</p>		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/instance-registry-service/en/latest/		
Service Endpoint	serviceregistry2.neanias.eu:2281 serviceregistry1.neanias.eu:2281 serviceregistry3.neanias.eu:2281 serviceregistry.dev.neanias.eu:2281		
Source Code	Backed by apache zookeeper at https://github.com/apache/zookeeper Packaged / integrated for NEANIAS: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/instance-registry-service/server		
Technical details	<p>The NEANIAS Service Instance Registry is backed by a distributed, highly available system. There will be multiple master and client nodes. All communications between master and client nodes will be encrypted.</p> <p>Master nodes are where data is stored and replicated. Multiple master node instances will be used to avoid data loss in failure scenarios.</p> <p>Client nodes will be responsible for monitoring the health status of the services that run in the node, and the also the node itself. Usage of client nodes will be optional, as services will be able to register directly as master nodes. They will be used then fine-grained information is needed to be monitored in order to determine the health status of the node.</p> <p>The main interface to NEANIAS Service Instance Registry will be an API. Authenticated services will be able to register, while others will be able to discover instances via this API. The API will be able to perform basic CRUD (create, read, update and delete) operations on services, and health checks. Discover queries will be executed and results will be responded in JSON format.</p>		

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	NEANIAS Service Instance Registry provides a command-line driven administrative User Interface to investigate status and registered services and provide health check information for each service.		
Core integration	The Service Instance Registry will integrate with a set of other core services to facilitate primarily monitoring and accounting of its usage. Integration with these services will be in a decoupled form, making this integration optional in setups that do not require such functionality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting – Accounting information on queries executed, etc (Optional) - Logging – Logging information on low level troubleshooting as well as higher level action auditing 		
Depends on	-		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A service registers itself so that it may be discovered by other services by a name and not depend on a fixed DNS/port binding. - A client service looks up for a service to utilize, not knowing its endpoint location. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	CITE	License	Apache 2.0
Current status	Initial service deployed operational for services to store and retrieve targeted service entries		
Future plans	Final service model update.		

7.5. Log Aggregation Service

Short Name	NEANIAS Logging	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Software library / Web service / UI web app	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Log Aggregation Service		
Service Category	C2 – Support Services		
Description	The NEANIAS Logging service provides an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can accumulate logs, that are generated in a distributed fashion, in a single centralized repository. This is achieved through well-defined endpoints and library utilities facilitating the transformation, enrichment and indexing of the log entries, that require no special hard dependencies from client apps. The central repository can be searched and further aggregated to		

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	<p>produce meaningful traces of user activity and facilitate troubleshooting and action auditing.</p> <p>Additionally, the service presents specific client technologies for service implementers to easily generate accounting information records.</p>
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/logging-service/en/latest/
Service Endpoint	https://logging.neanias.eu/
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/logging-service/server
Technical details	<p>The NEANIAS Logging Service is backed by an ELK stack. The ELK stack consists of an Elasticsearch (https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/) index backend that stores data and makes them searchable, Logstash (https://www.elastic.co/logstash/), that facilitates the transformation of log entries extraction of additional metadata and homogenization of logged entries, Kibana (https://www.elastic.co/kibana/), that offers visualization, aggregation and filtering graphical user interface over the indexed entries.</p> <p>To facilitate the aggregation of log, the Beats (https://www.elastic.co/beats/) framework for data shipping is used. Specifically, “beats” modules for both file and HTTP transfer is provided with supportive configuration to lower the integration barrier for all NEANIAS Service Providers. Yet clients are utilizing file-transfer as the least disruptive approach for the selected NEANIAS operation model.</p> <p>Templates for log entry formats are provided along with the respective Logstash transformation templates, which extracts a limited common set of information. This way it provides a homogenized set of data available, for log browsing and aggregation operations.</p> <p>A Kibana based solution offers browsing, filtering and visualization capabilities. Access to the Kibana graphical application is subject to authorization enforced by relevant access management plugins and integration with the NEANIAS AAI facilitates some degree of global policy enforcement through the central AAI service.</p> <p>The service is able to maintain invalid logging data, so that they are not lost, even if not able to project them along with properly formed ones.</p> <p>When EOSC presents a service for accounting information gathering, the service will adopt the interface and information model in order to supply the required accounting information.</p>
Core integration	<p>The NEANIAS Logging Service is largely an independent, core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. Still, it is possible to integrate it with a limited number of other NEANIAS Core services to enhance the usability of the service within the NEANIAS</p>

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	ecosystem. Integration with these services will be in a decoupled form, making this integration optional in setups that do not require such functionality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorization – Authentication for user and Service access can take place through the NEANAIS AAI service. Based on access token role mappings, the respective operations and data access will be made available 		
Depends on	Type-specific Storage services.		
Use cases	In the occurrence of an incident, an administrator, inspects the aggregated logs of the service to identify the issue occurring to a distributed, potentially not controlled by her, service component.		
EOSC Service	No (decision may be revised)		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	CITE	License	Mixed (Apache 2.0, Elastic License)
Current Status	<p>At this preliminary release, it is expected that basic configuration will be available to allow for direct aggregation of messages. Interface to browse the logs is available. Authentication / Authorization is implemented.</p> <p>Local agents' configuration to support distributed log aggregation, basic transformations to extract key characteristics. Integration with NEANIAS AAI for browsing logs has been implemented.</p>		
Future plans	Graphical user interface to browse and analyze log entries through a Kibana interface with direct access to the underlying index. Integration with the NEANAIS AAI to facilitate federated user role-based mapping to visualization and possibly administrative operations.		

7.6. Accounting Service

Short Name	NEANIAS Accounting	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Software library / Web service / UI web app	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Accounting Service		
Service Category	C2 – Support Service		
Description	The NEANIAS Accounting service provides an aggregation functionality through which NEANIAS services can centrally register accounting information, as this is gradually accumulated by their usage from the respective authorized clients. Different accumulation policies and		

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	<p>granularity of information can be supported depending on the respective services. The information model consists of globally defined key point indicators and the aggregation and reports generated based on these will be available for further usage, as appropriate.</p> <p>Although it is possible to foresee use cases where the aggregated information can be used for run-time decision making, throttling or altering the scope of user requests to consulting services, the primary focus of the service is to aggregate and report on the information.</p>
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/accounting-service/en/latest/
Service Endpoint	https://accounting.neanias.eu/
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/accounting-service/server
Technical details	<p>The NEANIAS Accounting Service is backed by a high performant NoSQL data store, to aggregate and track the aggregated accounting information.</p> <p>The information model that supported will be progressively refined. In order to comply with emerging suggestions within the EOSC environment, the following aspects of accounted information were investigated. This list is comprised of a proposed set of Service / Resource Level Targets and Performance Indicators towards which, relevant information can be gathered or be assisted in calculate by the respective service providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost • Requests • Users • Usage • Capacity • Coverage • Availability • Reliability • Serviceability/Durability • Other Performance Indicator Name/Value <p>For the aforementioned measures, values are supported as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unit (applicable to any measure) • Time • Information • Throughput <p>During the lifetime of the services, relevant indicators can be accumulated with different granularity and time frames. During this process, information will gradually be eligible to be folded to create aggregations, that will ensure in the long-term performance and</p>

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	<p>maintainability of the Accounting Service data structures, yet with some cost on granularity of historical data.</p> <p>To visualize and report on the aggregated information, dedicated reporting utilities are made available through a graphical user web interface. Access and authorization on the reported content are limited based on the NEANIAS AAI service.</p> <p>The Accounting Service offers aggregating and reporting functionality as well as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to keep malformed accounting records for future reference is provided, however data are not aggregated. - Ability to achieve records by trusted services on behalf of other services (AAI on behalf of targeted services). <p>The option to expose endpoints to cater for run time decision making logic, based on rule templates and threshold setting logic, is under consideration.</p> <p>If EOSC releases an Accounting Service API and data model, the service will comply with its specification and interoperate with it.</p>
Core integration	<p>The NEANIAS Accounting Service is largely an independent, core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as an aggregator of information. Still, it is possible to integrate it with a limited number of other NEANIAS Core services to enhance the usability of the service within the NEANIAS ecosystem. Integration with these services will be in a decoupled form, making this integration optional in setups that do not require such functionality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorization – Authentication for user and Service access can take place through the NEANIAS AAI service. Based on access token role mappings, the respective operations and data access will be made available - Logging – Logging information on low level troubleshooting as well as higher level action auditing
Depends on	Type-specific Storage services
Use cases	<p>A service provider wants to identify how much CPU time a particular user activity has occupied in the system.</p> <p>A service provider wants to know how many invocations per day were performed by a particular user.</p> <p>A service provider wants to know how much short-term storage is used by a user of a particular service.</p>
EOSC Service	No
Current TRL	TRL7
	Target TRL
	TRL8

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IPR	CITE	License	FOSS approved license Mixed (Apache 2.0, Elastic License) / CITE Permissive License / Other
Current Status	<p>Ability to register accounting information according to NEANIAS accounting model will be provided. Aggregated Visualization of the information. AAI integration. Delegation has been supported.</p> <p>Refinements on common accounting models. Aggregation utilities to ship data efficiently. Basic user interface with flexible data projection functionality.</p>		
Future Plans	Extended accounting model and basic reporting functionality.		

7.7. Notification Service

Short Name	NEANIAS Notification	Lead partner	CITE
Type	Web service / UI web app / UI Component	Contributors	CITE
Title	NEANIAS Notification Service		
Service Category	C2 – Support Service		
Description	<p>The NEANIAS Notification service acts as a generic notification provider for services that want to incorporate some sort of notification mechanism in their workflows. It allows generic configuration and parametrization of notification templates, giving configuration options for selected notification channels to users and allowing easy integration with other services that want to use its functionality</p>		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/notification-service		
Service Endpoint	https://notification.dev.neanias.eu/api/notification		
Source Code	<p>The Service Instance Registry is backed by an ASP.NET Core web application: https://code.cite.gr/git/cite/templates/aspnetcore-pomolo-notification</p> <p>Service packaging for NEANIAS is available at https://gitlab.neanias.eu/notification-service/server</p>		
Technical details	<p>The NEANIAS Notification service offers its functionality as a backend service, accepting notification events from other services. These events are interpreted through a set of pre-configured notification</p>		

	<p>flows and are delivered to its recipients based on the respective profile enabled.</p> <p>A descriptive list of the available features as well as corresponding technical implications, are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notification Channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In-App Notification (optional). ○ Mail. ○ SMS (optional not linked to the system). • Notification Policies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Global policies matching notification flows to acceptable notifier channels. ○ User level policies based on ordered user preferences. ○ Fall through available options depending on whether respective profile information is available. • Notification Tracking <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Depending on channel features. ○ Track delivery status of notification. • Retries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Configuration number of retries per notification flow. ○ Probabilistic retry intervals with progressive configurable delays. ○ Options to omit retries after long period of time. • Notification Templates <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Different templates per notification channel. ○ Support multiple locales. ○ Configurable and easily upgradable. • Adhoc notifications. • Interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Web API integration endpoints. ○ Asynchronous / Queue messages. ○ Administration Web App. ○ User Interface widget to display in-app notifications.
Core integration	<p>The NEANIAS Notification Service is largely an independent, core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as an event consumer from other services that want to use its functionality. Still, it is possible to integrate it with a limited number of other NEANIAS Core services to enhance the usability of the service within the NEANIAS ecosystem. Integration with these services will be in a decoupled form, making this integration optional in setups that do not require such functionality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorization – Authentication for user and Service access can take place through the NEANAIS AAI

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	service. Based on access token role mappings, the respective operations and data access will be made available <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Logging – Logging information on low level troubleshooting as well as higher level action auditing - Accounting – Accounting information will be maintained and shipped to the Accounting Service to account for the usage of the service resources and operations 		
Depends on	- External communication services for delivering messages via non in-app channels (e.g. mails, SMS gateways etc.)		
Use cases	Upon the completion of a long running task, a client service may request notifications to be sent to users to retrieve their results.		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	CITE	License	CITE Permissive License / Other
Current Status	Initial version offering single channel communication. Integration entry points. email channel integration. Extended notification templates implemented. Adhoc notifications supported and email channel enabled.		
Future Plans	Additional notification channels including mail and in-app notifications implemented (integrations may be needed with external providers to be enabled). User profile integrations (if provided by external service). Web user interface widget for in-app notification browsing.		

7.8. Data Depositing Service

Short Name	GARR Cloud Platform Object Store	Lead partner	GARR
Type	Web service / storage service	Contributors	GARR
Title	NEANIAS Object Storage Service		
Service Category	C2 - Data Management		
Description	The GARR Cloud Platform Object Storage Service will provide a RESTful API to store and retrieve objects (files) over the network and to manage object containers.		

Documentation	https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/openstack/rclone_quick_tutorial/		
Service Endpoint	https://dashboard.cloud.garr.it/project/containers/		
Source Code	https://github.com/ceph/ceph		
Technical details	<p>The GARR Cloud Platform Object Storage Service is provided through the OpenStack platform and offers a RESTful interface to store, retrieve and manage objects and containers (i.e. file and directory abstractions) and their metadata (a key=value format is supported). The GARR Cloud object storage service is based on Ceph, which provides the Rados Gateway daemon and implements transparent data redundancy and hardware failover.</p> <p>The GARR Cloud infrastructures are connected to the facilities of the international research community through the high-performance network links of the GÉANT network.</p>		
Core integration	The GARR Cloud Platform Object Storage Service is an independent core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as a consumer from other services that want to use its functionality.		
Depends on	-		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A user deposits or retrieves data contained in one or more files in consortium storage - A service deposits or retrieves data contained in one or more files in consortium storage 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	-
IPR	Ceph authors	License	LGPL, GPL, BSD
Current Status	Service is present. If required configuration/allocation changes may occur.		
Future Plans	The feasibility of geographical-level object redundancy is under investigation.		

7.9. Data Sharing Service

Short Name	DaShaS	Lead partner	NKUA
Type	Web service	Contributors	GARR

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Title	NEANIAS Data Sharing Service		
Service Category	C2 - Data Management		
Description	The Data Sharing Service (DaShaS) is a service used by the NEANIAS thematic services (and via them, by their end-users) to allow data stored internally in the NEANIAS Data Storage Service (DSS) to be shared between the end users, to be uploaded and/or downloaded by each user, and to be shared between services and users. This service is realized by a deployment of the NextCloud open-source project.		
Documentation	https://nextcloud.com/support/		
Service Endpoint	https://files.neanias.eu		
Source Code	https://github.com/nextcloud/server		
Technical details	The service is a standalone deployment of the NextCloud server, integrated with the NEANIAS AAI to allow seamless roaming of users from the NEANIAS services to this one and back. This a data repository, with no long-term preservation guarantees.		
Core integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AAI • Internal monitoring (Nagios) • External monitoring (Argo) 		
Depends on			
Use cases	a) User uploads a file, “shares” it with a service. The service prompts the user to pick the file that she has shared and perform its computation. b) Service computes an output result and stores it under its own account at NextCloud. Service then “shares” this result with the user, and the use is free to download the result to her own computer		
EOSC services integration	Eventually, EOSC AAI, EOSC monitoring (Argo) Potentially, EOSC portal, if service is deemed publishable		
EOSC Service	Potentially		
Current TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR	NKUA	License	Apache License
Current status	Deployed and operational, under the development and production domains, connected with AAI and monitored for uptime.		
MS7 expectation	If deemed publishable to EOSC, it will be fully integrated to EOSC at this point.		

7.10. Data exploration service

Short Name	Data Exploration	Lead partner	MEE0
Type	GUI / Web Service / API	Contributors	JACOBSUNI
Title	Data Exploration service		
Service Category	C2 - Data exploration		
Description	<p>The service allows the researchers to discover and explore a large variety and volume of geospatial datasets including Earth Observation and Planetary Science products driven by community needs. The service offers the following user interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the Explorer, a web-based graphic user interface to allow users to explore, access, process and download data. Explorer integrates also data processing functionalities and a dashboard for administrator to setup the application. • The Adamapi Application Processing Interfaces (APIs), that provide a python-library to directly access the ADAM data access and processing capabilities directly integrated in the user's code and applications. • the Jupyter Hub, a web-based processing environment to allow users to import, write and execute code that runs close to the data, exploiting the the adamapi functionalities on a remote computation environment. <p>The core services allow at performing essential operations on selected data thanks to the advance user interfaces like Jupyter notebook and REST/API. The standard data access will allow the implementation of operational services, the notebook will allow to make basic and advanced processing on-line.</p>		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c2-dataexploration/en/latest/		
Service Endpoint	https://explorer.adamplatform.eu/		
Source Code	Proprietary software		
Technical details	OGC services and OpenAPI backends will be accessed via browser and Jupyter/Python interfaces.		
Core integration	<p>This service needs integration with the following components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEANIAS AAI Authentication / Authorization - Accounting - Logging - AI Science Gateway (C3.1) - Spatial data stores (C4.4) 		
Depends on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial data stores (C4.4) 		

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	- External access services		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users search for datasets, data products based on metadata, geographic location (S1, Ax) - Users request data subsets and obtain (S2, S3, Ax) 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	MEEO	License	Proprietary Software
Current Status	The service is available and in operation to enable access to Copernicus, European Space Agency and other relevant data providers datasets. Integrated with NEANIAS AAI component, logging service, spatial data store and AI Science Gateway. Registered in the central service repository.		
Future Plans	Accounting integration (MS5) Registration of new datasets (MS6 - MS7) Continuous / real time registration of datasets		

7.11. SMTP Service

Short Name	SMTP e-mail Service	Lead partner	GARR
Type	Support service	Contributors	GARR
Title	SMTP e-mail Service		
Service Category	C2 Support Service		
Description	The NEANIAS SMTP e-mail service allows other services to send out e-mail messages on behalf of the neanias.eu domain.		
Documentation	http://www.postfix.org/documentation.html		
Service Endpoint	Smtplib.neanias.eu		
Source Code	https://github.com/vdukhovni/postfix		
Technical details	The NEANIAS SMTP e-mail service is based on the Postfix open-source mail transfer agent and it is hosted on a Virtual Machine on the GARR Cloud.		
Core integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notification service 		
Depends on	-		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service sends an e-mail message to a user • Service sends an e-mail message to a service provider 		

EOSC services integration	No		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL9	Target TRL	TRL9
IPR	Wietse Venema	License	IBM Public License or Eclipse Public License
Current Status	The service is available and in operation.		
Future Plans	-		

7.12. Computational resources access services

Computational resource access service provides a gateway to workflow, distributed processing engines or other computational capacity abstractions that will allow computational demands of NEANIAS to be spanned to other RIs, EOSC hub services or consortium resources (Includes access to Apache Spark / Hadoop).

The functionalities of this service can be implemented based on existing cloud/container orchestration tools. The service will be responsible to instruct the orchestration engine for instantiating the necessary computational resource(s) on the target cloud and for building the required infrastructure/ reference architecture on demand. Once the reference architecture has been built, access to the reference architecture is provided for the user.

7.12.1. GARR Cloud Platform Service

Short Name	GARR Cloud Platform Service	Lead partner	GARR
Type	Computational service, IaaS	Contributors	GARR
Title	GARR Cloud Platform Service		
Service Category	C2 - Computational services		
Description	The GARR Cloud Platform Service provides NEANIAS services with computational facilities in the form of virtual machines.		
Documentation	https://cloud.garr.it/doc/		
Service Endpoint	https://dashboard.cloud.garr.it/		
Source Code	https://opendev.org/explore/repos		
Technical details	The GARR Cloud Platform is based on OpenStack, an open-source software suite aimed at implementing cloud services in datacenters.		

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	<p>The GARR Cloud Platform is a multi-tenant environment spawning three different geographical regions. It is federated through the IDEM/eduGAIN AAI. The persistency layer relies on volumes backed by the Ceph system, which provides enhanced performance and data redundancy.</p> <p>The GARR Cloud infrastructures are connected to the facilities of the international research community through the high-performance network links of the GÉANT network.</p>		
Core integration	<p>The GARR Cloud Platform Service is an independent core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as a consumer from other services that want to use its functionality.</p>		
Depends on	-		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A user requests virtual machines for deployment of service. - Increased load of services leads to increase of allocated computational power. - A service requests computational power to execute computations. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	-
IPR	OpenStack Foundation	License	Apache License 2.0
Current Status	<p>The service is available at the GARR Cloud premises: https://cloud.garr.it. The current OpenStack version is "stein".</p>		
Future Plans	OpenStack version upgrades.		

7.12.2. GARR Container Platform Service

Short Name	GARR Container Platform Service	Lead partner	GARR
Type	Computational service, PaaS	Contributors	GARR
Title	GARR Container Platform Service		
Service Category	C2 - Computational services		
Description	<p>The GARR Container Platform Service provides NEANIAS services with the orchestration of computational facilities (CPU and GPU) besides storage and networking resource abstractions.</p>		
Documentation	https://cloud.garr.it/containers/		
Service Endpoint	https://k8s.cloud.garr.it/		

Source Code	https://github.com/kubernetes/kubernetes		
Technical details	<p>The GARR Container Platform is based on Kubernetes, a popular open-source platform for container orchestration which automates the deployment, management and scaling of applications.</p> <p>The GARR Container Platform is a multi-tenant environment whose authentication is managed by the GARR Cloud Platform OpenStack identity service (Keystone). The GARR Container Platform is deployed on bare metal to provide GPU resources which can be leveraged by Docker containers.</p> <p>The persistency layer relies on volumes backed by the Ceph system, which provides enhanced performance and data redundancy.</p> <p>The GARR Cloud infrastructures are connected to the facilities of the international research community through the high-performance network links of the GÉANT network.</p>		
Core integration	Although the GARR Container Platform Service depends on the GARR Cloud Service for user authentication, from the NEANIAS point of view it is an independent core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as a consumer from other services that want to use its functionality.		
Depends on	GARR Cloud Platform Service		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A user deploys a container-based service - A service spawns' containers to execute specific tasks 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	-
IPR	Cloud Native Computing Foundation	License	Apache License 2.0
Current Status	The GARR Container platform has been extended with two Kubernetes clusters (staging and production) dedicated to NEANIAS.		
Future Plans	The number of Kubernetes workers will be increased.		

7.12.3. GARR DaaS

Short Name	GARR DaaS	Lead partner	GARR
Type	Computational service, PaaS	Contributors	GARR
Title	GARR Deployment as a Service		
Service Category	C2 - Computational Services		
Description	The GARR DaaS provides NEANIAS services with computational facilities and application abstractions.		

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Documentation	https://cloud.garr.it/apps/		
Service Endpoint	https://daas-ct.cloud.garr.it/dashboard/		
Source Code	https://github.com/juju/juju		
Technical details	<p>The GARR DaaS is based on Juju, a free and open-source platform which can be used to deploy, scale and manage applications implemented through the composition of microservices.</p> <p>GARR DaaS allows users to deploy a wide range of applications on top of OpenStack through a web interface. These applications include tools which are aimed at data processing, such as Apache Spark, Hadoop, and Elasticsearch.</p> <p>The GARR Cloud infrastructures are connected to the facilities of the international research community through the high-performance network links of the GÉANT network.</p>		
Core integration	Although the GARR DaaS depends on the resources provided by the GARR Cloud Platform Service, from the NEANIAS point of view is an independent core service offering its functionality orthogonally from other services. It mostly acts as a consumer from other services that want to use its functionality.		
Depends on	GARR Cloud Platform Service		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A service provider deploys an application - A service deploys an application to execute a specific task 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL8	Target TRL	-
IPR	Canonical Ltd.	License	GNU Affero General Public License
Current Status	The service is already available at the GARR Cloud premises: https://cloud.garr.it/apps/daas/		
Future Plans	-		

8. C3 Artificial Intelligence services

C3 Artificial Intelligence services form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical Machine Learning (ML) workflow lifecycle, and that are also intended for composition of higher-level services.

In this section overall role of C3 services in NEANIAS is presented, then each service is described in alignment with the Service Description template adopted by the project.

8.1. The role of C3 services in NEANIAS

Figure 8: C3 Services Structure

Each C3 service represents the elements of a typical ML workflow lifecycle: initially, the model needs to be designed and implemented. In case the load of data exceeds the capabilities of a single workstation, the training should be offloaded to a distributed computational cluster. Depending on the model, different approaches for parallelization exist: parallel processing of Deep Neural Networks is fundamentally different than the training of other machine learning models, which could be efficiently decomposed to independent pieces. After a model is trained, serving and deployment requires dedicated resources.

8.2. C3.1 AI Science Gateway: service for development of ML models using Jupyter Hub

A development environment is necessary for the researchers to design, prototype, implement and test AI powered solutions. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project is preferred, with TensorFlow and Keras libraries.

Researchers are able to prototype solutions, while computationally intense training can be loaded to a computational cluster. Results can be visualized using the Visualization gateway (C4.2).

Figure 9: C3.1 Service Structure

Short Name	AI Gateway (C3.1)	Lead partner	SZTAKI
Type	Web service / UI web app	Contributors	INAF
Title	AI Gateway: service for Development of Machine Learning Model using Jupyter Hub		
Service Category	C3 AI Services		
Description	A web-based development environment for scientists to design, develop and evaluate machine learning solutions. After development, training of large models on big data can be done in a distributed environment, refer to C3.3 and C3.4.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-1-ai-gateway/en/latest		
Service Endpoint	https://ai-gateway.neanias.eu		
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c3-services/c3-1/service		
Technical details	<p>The core technology is Python, which is the most popular programming language in machine learning and data science scenes. Jupyter Hub is a multi-user development environment using the IPython interface, allowing code implementation and interpretation using a web interface. The kernel used include TensorFlow and Keras (www.keras.io), as the most popular libraries for neural network development, and other relevant packages as well.</p> <p>While the core is available as open source, some development on integrating the authentication protocols, and integrating relevant</p>		

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	functions of other services of the machine learning lifecycle (design, train, deploy).		
Core integration	Integration with the following is necessary: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorization - Storage access (temporary / permanent) - Computation access (direct or indirect) - Visualization 		
Depends on	C2 6.12 Data exploration service C2 6.13 Computational resources access service		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users of thematic services to access and develop machine learning models • Prototyping of machine learning algorithms 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	SZTAKI	License	FOSS, such as Apache
Current Status	AI Gateway is operational and supports the followings: multi environments, https, remote storage mounting, auto-deployment of demo applications, AAI integration, NEANIAS GitLab docker registry integration		
Future Plans	Migration to OS Kubernetes, integration to logging/accounting, version upgrade, integration to authorization, Integration to other C3 services		

8.3. C3.2 Serving trained ML models

Accessing trained models as web services should be possible seamlessly, with low efforts. To deploy a model as an API, large amount of memory is necessarily allocated and used constantly. Technically, there are multiple approaches to implement model serving, user and researcher-friendliness is prioritized.

Figure 10: C3.2 Service Structure

The fundamental idea behind model serving is that authorized clients are able to access prediction functionality without directly accessing the model, which would create a serious overhead caused by data transfer and memory allocation. Instead, a RESTful API based communication is preferred between a model server and the client. The server implements the model, allocates memory to efficiently handle prediction, and listens for input parameters on the interface. On request, prediction is done using the inner implementation, and the results are responded to the client.

Short Name	Model serving (C3.2)	Lead partner	ALTEC
Type	Web service	Contributors	SZTAKI, UNIMIB, INAF
Title	Serving trained ML models		
Service Category	C3 AI Services		
Description	Serving trained machine learning models as a web service.		
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-2-modelserving/en/latest/ 		
Service Endpoint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://minio.ml-models.dev.neanias.eu/ • http://yatai.ml-models.dev.neanias.eu/ • https://ai-gateway.neanias.eu 		
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c3-services/c3-2/service		
Technical details	A web interface with a REST API, which receives the input parameters and replies with the prediction(s). Implementation using TensorFlow Serve or Cortex currently seems suitable.		

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	On designing, the service must fit to C3.1 (and possibly C3.3 & C3.4), as the users should be able to deploy the designed and trained models seamlessly.		
Core integration	This service will probably need integration with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorisation - Storage Access - Computation Access 		
Depends on	C3.1 AI Gateway Might depend on C3.3, C3.4 C2 6.12 Data exploration service C2 6.13 Computational resources access service		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serving of trained models for production 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	ALTEC	License	FOSS, such as Apache
Current status	running on OS Kubernetes cluster (deployment, service and ingress), utilising NEANIAS docker registry, running under the *.dev.ml-models.neanias.eu domain, supports CI/CD pipeline to deploy the model automatically, supports authentication and authorization, running in staging, supports only http		
Future Plans	move service to prod environment, add https support, creating demo notebooks, automatic delegation of OpenID access to the notebook server, integration to logging, accounting		

8.4. C3.3 Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod

The training of deep neural networks on large amount of data requires a significant amount of processing time, which could be reduced by using GPU accelerators. The next step in increasing the performance is by using multiple GPU-enabled nodes in a distributed environment. While the parallel processing of deep neural networks has its limitations, Horovod (<https://eng.uber.com/horovod/>) is a robust tool which can be used to scale the training of TensorFlow based network implementations.

Figure 11: C3.2 Service Structure

Short Name	Horovod cluster (C3.3)	Lead partner	SZTAKI
Type	Web service	Contributors	INAF, UNIMIB
Title	Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod		
Service Category	C3 AI Services		
Description	The training of deep neural networks on big data takes significant time, even on GPU-enabled workstations. To increase efficiency, a distributed computation cluster should be used, where users can define models to train and collect results.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-3-horovod/en/latest/		
Service Endpoint	https://ai-gateway.neanias.eu		
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c3-services/c3-3/service		
Technical details	A Horovod based architecture of GPU-accelerated nodes, where the communication is based on the MPI protocol. The training jobs are queued, resulting model parameters and training logs are served to the user. Real-time tracking of the training process is possible, e.g. using TensorBoard.		
Core integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data discovery / Data publication - Storage access (temporary / permanent) - Computation access (direct or indirect) 		
Depends on	C31 AI Gateway		
Use cases	Scaled processing of computationally intense Deep Neural Network training		
EOSC Service	No (decision may be revised)		
Current TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8

IPR	SZTAKI	License	FOSS, such as Apache
Current Status	Deployed on GARR Openstack Cloud, utilizes Docker image registry, enhanced security configuration, automatic deployment with terraform, demo dataset		
Future Plans	Integration to C31, logging, accounting		

8.5. C3.4 Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML

Scaling up machine learning solutions other than deep neural nets (both for sake of classification, as well as for other tasks like regression and clustering) can be carried out using Apache Spark framework. The communication method and the data processing toolkit is a mature solution in distributed processing, and the ML library is built on these fundamental blocks. The Spark ML lib has API to Python, Java and R.

The structure of this service will be analogous as service C3.3, in an attempt to provide a uniform approach, programming interface and model to the developers employing these services.

Figure 12: C3.4 Service Structure

Short Name	Spark cluster (C3.4)	Lead partner	UNIMIB
Type	Web service	Contributors	SZTAKI
Title	Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML		
Service Category	C3 AI Services		
Description	In addition to models based on neural networks (that can benefit from a multi-GPU deployment, especially for learning phases) that are managed through C3.3, other AI techniques for classification, regression, or clustering tasks can however benefit from a deployment and execution in a distributed and memory-based architecture such as the one offered by Spark. In particular, C3.4 will support a variety of machine learning models such as Support Vector Machines, Decision		

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	Trees and ensemble models (Random Forests and Gradient Boosting) for both classification and regression, clustering algorithms, and other support functions that are useful in real-world, large scale, machine learning pipelines. The set of basic ML algorithms and models can also be extended by means of creative parallel computing approaches (e.g. parallel implementations of DBSCAN algorithm on top of Spark, an algorithm which is not natively provided by ML-Lib, are known and available).		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c3-4-spark/en/latest		
Service Endpoint	https://ai-gateway.neanias.eu		
Source Code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c3-services/c3-4/c3-4service		
Technical details	Apache Spark cluster with ML-lib, using a job queue, and transferring results and logs back to the users similarly as in C3.3.		
Core integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data discovery / Data publication - Storage access (temporary / permanent) - Computation access (direct or indirect) 		
Depends on	Might depend on C3.1		
Use cases	Use cases depending on the element (coming from thematic sectors and business sectors, or fundamental requirements of NEANIAS infrastructure)		
EOSC Service	No (decision may be revised)		
Current TRL	TRL6 (approaching 7)	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	SZTAKI	License	FOSS, such as Apache
Current Status	Prototype deployment for showcasing; experimental level. Configured external S3 storage as Hadoop FS. Added new use cases. Added possibility to deploy with spark operator. Updated to spark 3.1.1 that removes “experimental” tag on the deployment using Kubernetes as resource manager. Tested remote connection for spawning spark contexts.		
Future Plans	Integration to C31, Logging, accounting. Identify best solution for sharing data between spark workers.		

9. C4 Visualisation services

C4 or visualisation services in the context of NEANIAS, form the upper level of core services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and provide facilities that may reach all the way up to end user communities offering features of typical visualisation workflow lifecycles, and possibilities for composition of higher-level services. In this section the overall role of C4 services in NEANIAS is presented, then each service is described individually in alignment with the adopted service description template (see Appendix 1).

9.1. The role of C4 services in NEANIAS

Each C4 service represents the elements of a typical visualisation workflow lifecycle with focus on visual discovery frameworks (C4.1, VD-section 8.2), science gateways (C4.2, VG-section 8.2), a cross realities framework to support VR (C4.3, XR-section 8.3), and spatial data stores (C4.4, DS-section 8.4). The spatial data stores service underpins the science gateway framework whose workflows are based on the visual discovery framework and enable access to the mechanisms exposed through the XR toolkit; the overall schema is as in Figure 13.

Figure 13: C4 Services Schema

C4 activities identify underlying common themes and synergies, and apply cross-cutting glue and abstraction mechanisms, to realize a solid, modular, cross-sector, open-source, core pool of methods and tools to support visualisation services, leveraging on the resources available from NEANIAS delivery infrastructure. C4 will establish, implement and test such services to underpin a range of multi-faceted visualisation workflows, spanning from 2D/3D spatio-temporal to composite 2D/3D visuals of high dimensionality for computationally demanding cross reality applications, e.g. supporting mechanisms for scalable visualisation or production of assets for exploitation within game engines through VR headsets. When the load of data exceeds the capabilities of a single workstation, the workflow computation will be offloaded to distributed computational clusters. Depending on the tools deployed, different approaches

for parallelization will be exploited, in order to harvest optimally different types of underlying infrastructures, ranging from small-scale clusters with or without GPUs to large-scale heterogeneous architectures. Although the core functionalities developed in C4 services will allow customisation to serve specific needs of NEANIAS end-user communities, they are also expected to be able to generalise sufficiently over the core elements of thematic services to underpin demands of other EOSC end-user communities to reach far beyond NEANIAS. At start, all services were founded on existing TRL6 software solutions, which have meanwhile evolved towards TRL7 at present (see descriptions below) and are envisaged to be refined progressively to reach at least TRL 8 by the end of NEANIAS.

9.2. C4.1 Framework for Visual Discovery (VD)

C4.1 provides tools to support data intensive computing for visual scientific discovery (including research training and outreach) for observational data, theoretical simulations and 2D/3D tiling and maps. C4.1 consists of three distinct high-performance services for visual analytics from multidimensional data tables (VD-VisIVO), high-quality volume rendering of particle-based datasets exploiting a variety of parallel programming models leveraging upon heterogeneous infrastructures (VD-Splotch) and creation of interactive 2D/3D tiling and maps (VD-Maps). Details on these services are summarised in the tables below.

Figure 14: C4.1 services diagram

9.2.1. VD-VisIVO

Short Name	VD-VisIVO (C4.1.1)	Lead partner	INAF
Type	Software library / Command Line Interface	Contributors	UoP
Title	VisIVO		
Service Category	C4.1 Visual Discovery Framework		
Description	The service offers a framework for data intensive visual discovery for experiments and data analysis (including support for training of		

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	researchers and public outreach) tailored to the requirements of NEANIAS while reaching out to other EOSC end-user communities.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vd.html#vd-visivo		
End Point	Available from C4.2 Visualization Gateway Docker container: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/vd/vd-visivo		
Source Code	https://github.com/inaf-oact-VisIVO/VisIVOserver		
Technical details	The service makes available for data processing and visual discovery the suite of tools provided by VisIVO. VisIVO is specifically designed for distributed computing environments such as cloud infrastructures and offers a framework for exploration of large-scale scientific data-sets creating customized views of 3D renderings from multi-dimensional data tables from various sources.		
Core integration	See C4.2 Visualization Gateway		
Depends on	It depends on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C4.2 Visualization Gateway 		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within NEANIAS, all space thematic services (S1, S2, S3). • General users with multi-dimensional data in tabular formats (e.g. ASCII, CSV, VOTable, FITS, and others) wanting to explore data into multi-dimensional visual renderings. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	At a minimum TRL8
IPR	INAF	License	FOSS such as GNU General Public License (GPL).
Current Status	2020-08 the service has been released as Docker container. 2020-12 the service has been deployed within C4.2 Visualization Gateway under the NEANIAS infrastructure. 2021-2 Sample demo data and scripts provided to showcase. Aforementioned updates have elevated this service offering to TRL7.		
Future Plans	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates (M25). Final deployment (M32).		

9.2.2. VD-Plotch

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Short Name	VD-Splotch (C4.1.2)	Lead partner	UoP
Type	Software library / Command Line Interface	Contributors	INAF, SZTAKI
Title	Visual Discovery Framework - Splotch		
Service Category	C4.1 Visual Discovery Framework		
Description	The service offers a framework for data intensive visual discovery for experiments and data analysis (including support for training of researchers and public outreach) tailored to the requirements of NEANIAS while reaching out to other EOSC end-user communities.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vd.html#vd-splotch		
End point	Available from C4.2 Visualization Gateway Docker container: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/vd-splotch		
Source code	https://github.com/splotchviz/splotch		
Technical details	The service makes available for data processing and visual discovery the suite of tools provided by Splotch. Splotch supports very large-scale datasets and an array of diverse parallelisation models for fast, high-quality distributed particle volume rendering of particles coming from simulations, e.g. smoothed-particle hydrodynamics simulations and other sources.		
Core integration	See C4.2 Visualization Gateway		
Depends on	It depends on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C4.2 Visualization Gateway 		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within NEANIAS, all space thematic services (S1, S2, S3). • General users with cosmological simulation formats (e.g., Binary, Gadget, HDF5, Topsy, and others) wanting to explore data into high-quality particle-based visual renderings. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Start TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	At a minimum TRL8
IPR	UoP	License	FOSS such as GNU General Public License (GPL).
Current Status	2020-08 the service has been released as Docker container. 2020-12 the service has been deployed within C4.2 Visualization Gateway under the NEANIAS infrastructure.		

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	2021-2 sample demo data and scripts provided to showcase. Aforementioned updates have elevated this service offering to TRL7.
Future Plans	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates (M25). Final deployment (M32).

9.2.3. VD-Maps

Short Name	VD-Maps (C4.1.1.3)	Lead partner	CORONIS
Type	Web Service / Command Line Interface	Contributors	
Title	Visual Discovery Framework - 2D/3D Tiling and Maps		
Service Category	C4.1 Visual Discovery Framework		
Description	The service consists of a set of tools allowing the visualisation of large-scale large-resolution maps, either 2D (images), 2.5D (elevation/bathymetric maps) or 3D (3D meshes), in real-time on a web app. First, a conversion service transforming common single-file formats into multi-resolution tiled data structures will be provided. Then, we will also provide a generic web viewer using the created data structures.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vd.html#vd-maps		
End Point	https://vd-maps.neanias.eu/		
Source code	https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/vd-maps		
Technical details	The conversion service translating single file formats into a hierarchical data structure will be provided in the form of a set of command line tools within a container, and the resulting data structures will comply with OGC standards. Then, the web app allowing visualisation of such data structures will be implemented using CesiumJS library (www.Cesium.com/cesiumjs/).		
Core integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common user interface components • NEANIAS AAI Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure Service • Data sharing service • Log aggregation service • Accounting service 		

Depends on	It may depend on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C4.1.1 VD-VisIVO • C4.1.2 VD-Splotch • C4.4 DS 		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within NEANIAS, all underwater thematic services (U1, U2, U3). • General users with GIS data in common formats (GDAL-compliant) wanting to convert their data into multiresolution tiled data structures. 		
EOSC Service	No		
Start TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	At a minimum TRL8
IPR	CORONIS	License	FOSS such as GNU General Public License (GPL).
Current Status	First version provided functionality showcase for tiled maps creation from 2D/2.5D maps, with software released in a container. Deployment within NEANIAS infrastructure of a web app providing a UI for accessing the tiling functionality and a first version of the viewer for 2D and 2.5D data. It is integrated with NEANIAS AAI, logging and accounting core services and follows the NEANIAS common UI template. (M14)		
Future Plans	Service integrated with all other core services of NEANIAS, improved version of web app and its Cesium viewer(M25) Final deployment of the tile maps creation service and the Cesium web app (M32)		

9.3. C4.2 Visualisation Gateway (VG)

C4.2 provides a testbed environment for designing, rapid prototyping, implementing and formally validating complex scientific visualisation solutions realising common data exploration workflows. To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, the popular IPython based Jupyter Hub project has been selected. C4.2 is built upon this and the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.2 services are envisaged to be interconnected with C3.1 AI Gateway services to allow visualisations of AI powered solutions, C4.3 to underpin powerful VR solutions and C4.4 to facilitate end-user data accessibility. C4.2 is deployed in a way that can be fully embedded within the relevant workflows of end-user communities activities, while exploiting a range of diverse parallelisation models and infrastructure accelerator capabilities for optimal performances.

Figure 15: C4.2 services diagram showing: a) core dependencies / functionalities and b) linking to AI gateway

Short Name	VG (C4.2)	Lead partner	INAF
Type	Web/Service UI Web App	Contributors	UoP
Title	Visualization Gateway		
Service Category	C4.2 Visualization Gateway		
Description	The service offers a web-based interactive environment for designing, developing and evaluating complex, scalable visualisation scenario solutions. Big data are handled in a distributed environment leveraging on heterogeneous infrastructures and based on the services implemented in C4.1. The visualisation outcomes are delivered in ways allowing full integration with relevant scientific workflow.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/vg.html		
End point	https://vis-gateway.neanias.eu/		
Source code	Kubernetes deployment configuration: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/vg		
Technical details	The service essentially offers an interactive framework, based on Jupyter Hub sharing methodologies and similar approaches with the C3.1 AI gateway to enable optimal visualisations of complex scientific tasks with outcomes being possible to be seamlessly and intuitively integrated in scientific workflows production pipelines.		
Core integration	It integrates with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogue service • AAI Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure Service 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logging • Accounting • Data sharing service 		
Depends on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C4.1.1 VD-VisIVO • C4.1.2 VD-Splotch • Computational resources access service (Kubernetes cluster) 		
Use cases	a) NEANIAS space research services for visualization (S1) and structure detection with Machine Learning (S3) b) Use Cases from C4.1.1 (VD-VisIVO), C4.1.2 (VD-Splotch)		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL7	Target TRL	At a minimum TRL8
IPR	INAF/UoP	License	FOSS such as GNU General Public License (GPL).
Current Status	2020-08 planned month of first release with core visualisation Python packages to support NEANIAS outreach and engagement plan. 2020-12 the service was deployed on the NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster and integrated with NEANIAS AAI (MS4). 2021-02 the service was integrated with NEANIAS data sharing service (based on NextCloud) including demo data to test the underlying Visual Discovery environments.		
Future Plans	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core services (integration with logging and accounting is ongoing) and with other thematic services based on use cases requirements updates. Final deployment (M32)		

9.4. C4.3 Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)

C4.3 will provide a toolkit underpinning an environment for designing, implementing and validating complex visualisation solutions exposed to end-users via Cross Realities (XR) mechanisms, e.g. those based on Virtual Reality (VR) or Augmented Reality (AR). To serve as a universal core service for multiple users, popular software frameworks and technologies have been selected based on a set of components used by an existing TLR6 software solution called Astra Data Navigator (ADN), e.g. the frameworks provided by the game engine Unity and HTC Vive headset. Such components will support interactive data exploration and navigation mechanisms e.g., for advanced comparisons in multidimensional and multifrequency datasets for research and public outreach. C4.3 services will be built upon extending existing components with a focus on providing services with enhanced realism,

precision and usability along a number of aspects relating to enriched user experiences covering e.g., novel navigation mechanisms and VR technologies and seamless integration of large-scale catalogues. C4.3 will exploit the framework for visual discovery developed in C4.1. C4.3 services are envisaged to be interconnected seamlessly with C4.2 to furnish complex visualisation workflows and C4.4 to underpin advanced data access. The components identified so far consist of a data connector for retrieving, in a generic way, data coming from different sources (individual files or databases) and a positioning manager providing the capabilities to retrieve specific data about position/rotation of particular objects for specific temporal instants. The implementation of the later is envisaged to deploy cloud infrastructures to extract the relevant information through Spice kernels. As part of the XR toolkit various VRviewers are expected to be realised visualising not only space objects but also 3D data of various typologies of interest to other NEANIAS domains (e.g. atmospheric).

Figure 16: C4.3 services diagram

Short Name	XR (C4.3)	Lead partner	ALTEC
Type	Software / Web Service	Contributors	UoP
Title	Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)		
Master element	N/A		
Description	The service offers a cloud enabled toolkit facilitating interactive data exploration and navigation to underpin VR applications.		
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/xr.html		
End Point	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://pms.neanias.eu/ 		
Source code	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/xr/dcs https://gitlab.neanias.eu/c4-service/xr/pms 		

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Technical details	The service is founded upon the Astra Data Navigator (ADN), which is a 3D visualization environment within the Unity game engine for large stellar catalogues. A number of services will be targeted for data pre-processing to prepare VR enabled assets from a variety of sources focusing on realism, precision and usability of the relevant workflows and covering aspects such as sophisticated navigation, real-time VR tracking and seamless integration of large-scale catalogues.		
Core integration	It is integrated with the following services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalogue service (monitoring) • Common user interface components • AAI Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure Service • Computational resources access service 		
Depends on	It may depend on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C4.1.1 VD-VisIVO • C4.1.2 VD-Splotch • C4.1.3 VD-Maps • C4.4 DS 		
Use cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Within NEANIAS, all space thematic services (S1, S2, S3). • Use cases of C4.1 services 		
EOSC Service	No		
Current TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8 as a minimum
IPR	ALTEC/UOP	License	FOSS such as GNU General Public License (GPL).
Current Status	2020-08 Position Manager Service (PMS) module deployed on dev environment, integrated with AAI service. 2020-12 PMS module integrated with AAI, logging and accounting services. 2021-02 Data Connector Service (DCS) module deployed on dev environment, integrated with AAI, logging and accounting services. 2021-04 PMS and DCS modules deployed on staging environment in a stable version.		
Future Plans	Integrated showcasing (M25). Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates. Final deployment (M32).		

9.5. C4.4 Spatial Data Stores (DS)

Spatial Data Stores provides a proper set of reference systems and data structures useful to exploit the spatial features of catalogues and datasets. It is exposed to the C2 Data Exploration Service and to the C4.3 Visualization Gateway both integrated to core services for authentication, logging, accounting, UI and computing.

Figure 17: C4.4 services diagram

Short Name	Spatial data store (C4.4)	Lead partner	JACOBS
Type	DBMS	Contributors	MEEO
Title	Spatial data store		
Master element	N/A		
Description	<p>Spatial data stores allow data to be referenced, query and retrieved, based on a given location (e.g., the globe, the Earth, planetary bodies with a proper reference system or the sky).</p> <p>Earth Observation data, including Copernicus datasets and products, are referenced in the ADAM Data Access System (DAS), a software module that manages a large variety of geospatial information that feature different data format, geographic / geometric and time resolution. It allows accessing, visualizing, sub-setting, combining, processing, downloading all data sources simultaneously. The DAS exposes OGC Open Search and Web Coverage Service (WCS 2.x) interfaces that allow discovering available datasets and subset them in any dimension with a single query.</p> <p>Planetary bodies differ from the sky on their concavity and dimensions, bodies being concave surfaces of limited sizes whereas</p>		

 Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

	the sky is convex and limitless. A coordinate reference system at the interface layer on spatial data bases is responsible to translate user requests into internal data reference.
Documentation	https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/c4-services/en/latest/services/ds.html https://docs.aws.amazon.com/AmazonS3/latest/dev/Introduction.html
End Point	The access to the storage layer is implemented through C2 Data exploration service.
Source Code	Software information has been provided for the C2 Data Exploration Service. See the related section.
Technical details	<p>ADAM, Geoserver, MongoDB, PostgreSQL & PostGIS are systems designed to handle spatial data storage and the operations to query/retrieve such data sets.</p> <p>ADAM provides seamless full data cycle management functionalities to explore spatial distribution and temporal evolution of various geophysical and geospatial information as well as to integrate and execute data processing functionalities at scale.</p> <p>MongoDB, on the other hand, is designed to work with unstructured data, text, numbers and vectors, it has applicability on spatial vector data -- data representing polygons used to define observation footprints, for example.</p> <p>PostgreSQL & PostGIS. PostGIS provides support for geographic objects allowing location queries to be run in SQL and follows the Open Geospatial Consortium's "Simple Features for SQL Specification" and has been certified as compliant with the "Types and Functions" profile. Furthermore, PostGIS enjoys wide support from various third-party open source and proprietary tools as QGIS.</p> <p>Geoserver comes as a good alternative for small size, heterogeneous data sets, as a volatile data storage system to publish high-level or temporary user products.</p> <p>The data store, provided by the ADAM service, is a composition of MongoDB, PostgreSQL/PostGIS and GeoServer organized to provide OGC features and raster data through the graphical exploratory interface as well as the low-level, programmatic ADAM-API.</p>
Core integration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Authentication and Authorization b. Storage access services
Depends on	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data exploration services
Use cases	a) Atmospheric (Ax) and Space research services (S1) to manage space data

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	b) Provide OGC compliant services for data access (Ax, S1, S2)		
EOSC Service	No		
Start TRL	TRL6	Target TRL	TRL8
IPR	JACOBS MEEO	License	GPL v3.0 proprietary software
Current Status	Service setup / First version for showcasing (M14)		
Future Plans	Integrated showcasing (M25). Final deployment (M32)		

10. Workplan – Timeline

The following section will overview the four stages of each service during the lifetime of the project. The four stages will represent four milestones during the development and delivery of the services. The table below has the four stages/ milestones in columns for which each service defines its expected status. The evolution of the services starts from standalone service till the fully integrated version.

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Access Gate & Catalogue Portal	Production and Beta deployment. Extended with Web UI\UX functionality for a) adjusting to NEANIAS common UI templates, b) Connecting to NEANIAS AAI, c) addressing NEANIAS service providers' needs for service classification and management at the UI, d) UI support for the EOSC model (EOSC Profiles). NEANIAS Services mapped to EOSC profiles and populated the catalogue.	EOSC integration for updating EOSC-onboarded services Integration with ticketing system and improvements. Accommodate changes \ new additions in EOSC Profiles (the description of providers and services) posed by EOSC portal
Catalogue Service	Production and Beta deployment. Extended with functionality for a) addressing NEANIAS service providers' needs for service classification and management, b) new EOSC model for service metadata (EOSC Profiles). NEANIAS Services mapped to EOSC profiles and populated the catalogue.	EOSC integration for updating EOSC-onboarded services. Issue fixing and improvements. Accommodate any changes in EOSC Profiles (the description of providers and services) posed by EOSC portal.
Research Product Catalogue	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.	

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Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Data Validation Service	The service has not been deployed. Initial validation dealt with metadata for publishing datasets. Re-design has been completed and core elements have been selected. Integration / implementation will start after M18.	<p>At MS6 a first version deployed with a local database, REST interface only, provided to support integration with other services.</p> <p>Eventually both Web UI and REST interfaces will be deployed and become operational, without automated rating. If automated rating proves viable, it will be experimented with.</p>
Web UI toolkit and template	Generic stylesheet and color guidelines for thematic landing pages (see e.g. implementation for the SPACE sector: https://thematic.neanias.eu/SPACE/ and ATMO-FLUD service: https://atmo-flud.neanias.eu/). Menu templates and button templates.	Specific components for service exposure as and when requested.
OpenDMP Software	Public release to accommodating observations of NEANIAS users. Deployed on OpenAIRE as Argos. Integration with EOSC AAI has been implemented, however it is not enabled in the OpenAIRE deployment. As such users cannot hop from any NEANIAS service onto Argos directly, and this is scheduled for MS6. Integration with Zenodo (set for MS6) is provided by Argos.	Updated user functionality (template management) and AAI integration (NEANIAS / Argos).

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Data Publishing service	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.	<p>When we presented Zenodo and its REST API to the service providers of the NEANIAS thematic services, we got the following feedback: Even though Zenodo allows one to use this API to upload a “record” (in Zenodo terminology), this record appears owned by whoever posted it, which in our case would be the service provider’s account at Zenodo. However, the actual owner of the record should be the end-user and not the service, as the end-user should be able to manage the record for its lifetime, after the initial upload (e.g., modify it to her own will). We investigated with Zenodo and they don’t support a “transfer of ownership” functionality.</p> <p>Due to the issue above (in current status), we are investigating the feasibility of producing a (core) service that will take the dataset and its metadata from the thematic service, allows the end-user to sign-on to Zenodo with her own credentials, and then upload the dataset under her/his own name. We will report in a refresh of this deliverable on the progress of this exercise</p>
Persistent Identifier Service	The Zenodo service is already fully operational.	

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure Service	Production realm, dev and staging are made available. Integration with NEANIAS Logging and NEANIAS Accounting services has been made available. Integration with NEANIAS Logging and NEANIAS Accounting services has been made available. Extensions for delivery of user information to services have been implemented.	EOSC AAI integration will be enabled. Enhancements on the integration with the NEANIAS Accounting Service. Alpha availability of fine-grained resource level authorization will be evaluated. Additional targets of self-management and application of central token issuing for services will be considered depending on additional resources to be made available. In final version further authorization capabilities will be considered.
Configuration Management Service	Initial service delivery dependable for services to store and retrieve public configuration. Deployed in infrastructure.	Major service update. Integration with logging / accounting.
Service Instance Registry	Initial service deployed operational for services to store and retrieve targeted service entries	Final service model update.

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Log Aggregation Service	<p>At this preliminary release, it is expected that basic configuration will be available to allow for direct aggregation of messages. Interface to browse the logs is available. Authentication / Authorization is implemented.</p> <p>Local agents' configuration to support distributed log aggregation, basic transformations to extract key characteristics. Integration with NEANIAS AAI for browsing logs has been implemented.</p>	<p>Graphical user interface to browse and analyze log entries through a Kibana interface with direct access to the underlying index. Integration with the NEANAIS AAI to facilitate federated user role-based mapping to visualization and possibly administrative operations.</p>
Accounting Service	<p>Ability to register accounting information according to NEANIAS accounting model will be provided. Aggregated Visualization of the information. AAI integration. Delegation has been supported.</p> <p>Refinements on common accounting models. Aggregation utilities to ship data efficiently. Basic user interface with flexible data projection functionality.</p>	<p>Extended accounting model and basic reporting functionality.</p>
Notification Service	<p>Initial version offering single channel communication. Integration entry points. eMail channel integration.</p>	<p>Additional notification channels including mail and in-app notifications implemented (integrations may be needed with external providers to be enabled). User profile integrations (if provided by external service).</p>

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
	Extended notification templates implemented. Adhoc notifications supported and eMail channel enabled.	Web user interface widget for in-app notification browsing.
Data Depositing Service	Service is present. If required configuration/allocation changes may occur.	The feasibility of geographical-level object redundancy is under investigation.
Data Sharing Service	Deployed and operational, under the development and production domains, connected with AAI and monitored for uptime.	If deemed publishable to EOSC, it will be fully integrated to EOSC at this point.
Data exploration service	The service is available and in operation with a set of data query able (e.g. Copernicus datasets). Integrated with NEANIAS AAI component, logging service, spatial data store and AI Science Gateway. Registered in the central service repository.	Accounting integration (MS5) Registration of new datasets (MS6 - MS7) Continuous / real time registration of datasets

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
SMTP e-mail Service	The service is available and in operation.	
GARR Cloud Platform Service	The service is available at the GARR Cloud premises: https://cloud.garr.it . The current OpenStack version is "stein".	OpenStack version upgrades.
GARR Container Platform Service	The GARR Container platform has been extended with two Kubernetes clusters (staging and production) dedicated to NEANIAS.	The number of Kubernetes workers will be increased.
GARR Deployment as a Service	The service is already available at the GARR Cloud premises: https://cloud.garr.it/apps/daas/ .	-
AI Science Gateway: service for Development of Machine Learning Model using JupyterHub	AI Gateway is operational and supports the followings: Multi Environments, HTTPS, Remote storage mounting, Auto-deployment of demo applications, AAI integration, NEANIAS GitLab docker registry integration	Migration to OS Kubernetes, integration to logging/accounting, version upgrade, integration to authorization, Integration to other C3 services

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Serving trained ML models	Running on OS Kubernetes cluster (deployment, service and ingress), utilising NEANIAS docker registry, running under the *.dev. ml-models.neanias.eu domain, supports CI/CD pipeline to deploy the model automatically, supports authentication and authorization, running in staging, supports only http	Move service to prod environment, add HTTPS support, creating demo notebooks, automatic delegation of OpenId access to the notebook server, integration to logging, accounting
Distributed Multi-GPU training of large ML models using Horovod	Deployed on GARR OpenStack Cloud, utilizes Docker image registry, enhanced security configuration, automatic deployment with terraform, demo dataset	Integration to C31, logging, accounting
Distributed Machine Learning using SparkML	Prototype deployment for showcasing; experiment level. Configured S3 storage as Hadoop FS. Added new Use cases. Added possibility to deploy with spark operator.	Integration to C31, logging, accounting
Visual Discovery Framework - VisIVO	2020-08 the service has been released as Docker container. 2020-12 the service has been deployed within C4.2 Visualization Gateway under the NEANIAS infrastructure. 2021-02 provided sample demo data and scripts to showcase.	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates (M25). Final deployment (M32).

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
Visual Discovery Framework - Splotch	2020-08 the service has been released as Docker container. 2020-12 the service has been deployed within C4.2 Visualization Gateway under the NEANIAS infrastructure. 2021-02 provided sample demo data and scripts to showcase.	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates (M25). Final deployment (M32).
Visual Discovery Framework - 2D/3D Tiling and Maps	First version provided functionality showcase for tiled maps creation from 2D/2.5D maps, with software released in a container. Deployment within NEANIAS infrastructure of a web app providing a UI for accessing the tiling functionality and a first version of the viewer for 2D and 2.5D data. It is integrated with NEANIAS AAI, logging and accounting core services and follows the NEANIAS common UI template. (M14)	Service integrated with all other core services of NEANIAS, improved version of web app and its Cesium viewer(M25) Final deployment of the tile maps creation service and the Cesium web app (M32)
Visualization Gateway	2020-08 planned month of first release with core visualisation Python packages to support NEANIAS outreach and engagement plan. 2020-12 the service was deployed on the NEANIAS Kubernetes Cluster and integrated with NEANIAS AAI (MS4). 2021-02 the service was integrated with NEANIAS data sharing service (based on NextCloud)	Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core services (integration with logging and accounting is ongoing) and with other thematic services based on use cases requirements updates. Final deployment (M32)

Core Service	Current Status	Future Plans
	including demo data to test the underlying Visual Discovery environments.	
Toolkit for Cross Realities (XR)	2020-08 PMS module deployed on dev environment, integrated with AAI service. 2020-12 PMS module integrated with AAI, logging and accounting services. 2021-02 DCS module deployed on dev environment, integrated with AAI, logging and accounting services. 2021-04 PMS and DCS modules deployed on staging environment in a stable version.	Integrated showcasing (M25). Updates of software to provide integration with other NEANIAS core/thematic services based on use cases requirements updates. Final deployment (M32).
Spatial data stores	Service setup / First version for showcasing (M14)	Integrated showcasing (M25). Final deployment (M32)

11. Conclusions

This deliverable aims a) to summarize the design principles followed for implementing the NEANIAS core services b) to overview the architecture which provides a framework for combining the core services and c) to introduce the C1/C2/C3/C4 core services with their most important functionalities and main characteristics being developed as core services for this project.

This deliverable is an updated version of deliverable D6.1 written at the early stage of the project. Therefore, at the time of writing the previous version, the project had not much experience and tried to focus on covering the expectations raised in the proposal. During the last twelve months, many experiences gained, new requirements raised, some aspects turned to be less important, some new arrived and some new solutions found. In Section 2 the most important updates - happened since D6.1 - have been summarized shortly while the actual status has been updated in details in the rest of the sections. Since this deliverable has been designed to be a self-contained document the structure is kept regardless of the quality and quantity of changes in the content.

Section on design principles is focusing on service-oriented architecture with high-degree of interoperability through the utilisation of REST paradigm and standards in communication and FAIR principles in data handling. Guidelines for operating services and for the most important security aspects are also collected. The AAI security concept and policy have been introduced in details since one of the most commonly used function in the core services will be authentication/ authorisation/ identification. Similar importance is given for user interface design where basic principles are declared. Finally, the most recommended technologies are overviewed on the different fields such as programming languages, development/data management/AI and other frameworks.

Section on system architecture is giving a detailed overview of the NEANIAS ecosystem being developed within the framework of the NEANIAS project. The deliverable provides a top-to-bottom overview. It starts with a high-level architecture diagram summarising the abstract relation among the Basic / Advance core services and Thematical ones. Then a logical architecture view with the fundamental building blocks is presented by specifying 5 levels of abstraction. In order to support the common internal operation of the core services, an internal lifecycle is proposed. Finally, the hypothetical deployment of the NEANIAS services is presented to help the reader understand the overall architecture of the ecosystem.

Fundamental resources abstractions are specified and detailed by introducing three categories, such as storage, compute and other. These subsections summarize the identified resources to be utilized for testing, development and operation of the services introduced in the next section of the deliverable.

In the next 4 sections, the list of C1/C2/C3/C4 services are specified with their most important attributes. C1 services provide the necessary tools for NEANIAS services to be discoverable and accessible and integrated with EOSC hub. C2 services form the lower level of services in the NEANIAS ecosystem and are the ones that deliver access to various levels of resources that serve the use cases of the project. C3 services provide features of a typical Machine Learning (ML) workflow lifecycle, while C4 services provide facilities that may reach up to the end user offering features of a typical visualisation workflow lifecycle.

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Finally, a workplan is given to overview the current status of the services and their planned improvements for the rest of the project.

Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications (update)

References

[1] NEANIAS WP6 Collaboration, "D6.1: Core Services Architecture, Design Principles and Specifications," NEANIAS, 2020.

[2] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, "D7.4: Infrastructure's integration report (interim)," NEANIAS, 2021.

[3] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, "D7.1: Delivery Activities Methodology and Plan," NEANIAS, 2020.

[4] NEANIAS WP9 Collaboration, "D9.1: Exploitation plan, report on plan for refined exploitation targets and activities to be performed by the project and its members," NEANIAS, 2020

[5] NEANIAS WP7 Collaboration, "Operation Activities Report (interim)," NEANIAS, 2021

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication Authorization Infrastructure
ACL	Access Control List
API	Application Programming Interface
CSS	Cascading Style Sheet
DCS	Data Connector Service
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FOSS	Free and Open Source Software
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
JS	JavaScript
JVM	Java Virtual Machine
MVC	Model-View-Controller
PMS	Position Manager Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
RI	Research Infrastructure
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SPA	Single Page Application
VisIVO	Visualization Interface for the Virtual Observatory

Appendix 1 – Service Description Template

Short Name	Short name for the service	Lead partner	Partner responsible as per DOA or post-DOA agreement
Type	Software library / Web service / UI web app / UI Component	Contributors	Partners contributing to the service
Title	Full element name		
Service Category	Service this element belongs to or specializes or extends (if applicable)		
Description	Brief description of the element oriented to the general public covering objectives and main functional outcome.		
Documentation	Link to service documentation.		
Service Endpoint	Link to service access endpoint (if any).		
Source Code	Link to service source code.		
Technical details	Technical details about the service, w.r.t. techniques, protocols etc. Also describe whether the element is web-ui accessible or a background service.		
Core integration	Describe integration of the service with fundamental core services of NEANIAS, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Authentication / Authorisation - Accounting - Logging - Data discovery / Data publication - Storage access (temporary / permanent) - Computation access (direct or indirect) - Visualisation - other 		
Depends on	Other services or components the element depends on, either in NEANIAS or other infrastructures.		
Use cases	Use cases depending on the element (coming from thematic sectors and business sectors, or fundamental requirements of NEANIAS infrastructure)		
EOSC Service	Is published in EOSC? (Yes/No)		
Current TRL	TRL6/TRL7/TRL8/TRL9	Target TRL	TRL8/TRL9

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IPR	Name the main IPR holder of the service (expected to coincide with partner responsible).	License	Name the license under which the code of the element may be delivered
Current Status	Describe the current status.		
Future Plans	Describe the future plans e.g., expected status of the service at MS6, MS6 Integrated showcasing (M25); Describe expected status of the service at MS7, final deployment (M32) (EOSC integration is mandatory for services targeting EOSC)		